

WP5 – DEMAND SIDE D5.5 - DATA ANALYSIS UPDATE – 07/08/2025

IULM TEAM

Ferri Giulia, Andrea Miconi, Elisabetta Risi, Nello Barile

This report provides a preliminary overview of the interpretations developed by the IULM research team based on the analysis conducted. The following pages present a summary of the codes and categories identified within each main thematic area.

Please note that this document does not represent the final Deliverable 5.5. Rather, it serves as an initial presentation of both the coding framework and the key insights emerging from our team's work.

Table of Contents

- DEMOCRACY** 3
 - 1.1 Democracy Ideal 3
 - 1.2 Democracy Opinion 7
 - 1.3 Democracy Expectations 15
 - 1.4 Democracy Threats 18
 - 1.5 Democracy Trust & Distrust 21
- MEDIA’S ROLE IN DEMOCRACY** 26
 - 2.1 Idea of Media’s Role in democracy 26
 - 2.2 Opinion Media’s role in democracy 28
 - 2.3 Expectations of the democratic role of the media 35
 - 2.4 Media Social Impact 37
 - 2.5 Media Trust & Distrust 38
 - 2.6 Media Habits 41
- POLITICAL PARTICIPATION** 43
 - 3.1 Activities 43
 - 3.2 Barriers to participation 46
 - 3.3 Encouragements to participation 50
- PARTECIPATION THROUGH THE MEDIA** 54
 - 4.1 Positive aspects 54
 - 4.2 Negative aspects 55
- Annex** 57

Introduction

This report offers a preliminary overview of the data analysis conducted by the IULM team as part of a broader research initiative. Its primary aim is to provide other teams with a structured pathway through the codes and categories that emerged from the analysis, carried out using a Grounded Theory approach. Rather than presenting final interpretations, this document serves as a tool to navigate the analytical process and to share insights into the interpretative structures identified thus far.

Given the extensive volume of material—over 111 files—the team opted to organize the report according to the original thematic structure that also guided the design of the interviews and focus groups. The analysis therefore begins with participants’ reflections on democracy, including their opinions, levels of trust, and related expectations. It then proceeds to examine the perceived role of the media in democratic life, continuing to explore the interpretative categories that emerged in relation to ideals, public opinion, trust, and media practices.

This same thematic lens is applied to the investigation of political participation, both in traditional forms and through the use of media. Throughout, the focus remains on highlighting the most salient categories identified across the data corpus.

To support readability and provide a concise overview, the report concludes with a summary table of the key codes and categories. It is important to note that this report represents an intermediate step in the overall analytical process. Further interpretative work—both in-depth and comparative, particularly in relation to emerging national specificities—is ongoing and will be shared in the coming weeks, with a projected release in early September.

DEMOCRACY

1.1 Democracy Ideal

Analysis of the collected testimonies highlights an idea of democracy that extends beyond the institutional sphere and takes root in individuals' everyday lives. Democracy is not merely a form of government or a set of procedural rules; it is a lived experience, shaped by expectations, ambivalences and aspirations. Democracy emerges as a relational and symbolic arena where the tensions between individual rights, collective recognition, and practical participation are played out. Specifically, among the main categories that emerged, there are:

1. Freedom as democracy's cornerstone and its limitation

Freedom is the most recurrent and shared value among the participants. It takes many forms: freedom of expression, of choice, of movement, of self-determination. It is perceived as the essential prerequisite for democratic life, to the extent that its exercise becomes an indicator of the very quality of democracy.

Czech: [FG. 2] *“Participant 14: The ability to express what I think, but also bearing the risk that if my opinion isn't trendy, meaning it's not aligned with what some media are promoting, it could be discredited in some way”*

France: [Int.10] *“Democracy, for me, it's freedom of expression. It's the freedom to choose a religion to have or not. It's freedom, it's simply freedom. That's what democracy is for me”*

A crucial dimension of this freedom, emerging across several national contexts, is the freedom of information—the right to access independent, uncensored, and impartial media. Participants consistently identified a free press as indispensable to democratic functioning, highlighting its role in enabling informed decision-making, citizen participation, and accountability of those in power. Without this freedom, the democratic process itself is seen as compromised.

Estonia: [Int. 3] *“A crucial dimension of this freedom, emerging across several national contexts, is the freedom of information—the right to access independent, uncensored, and impartial media. Participants consistently identified a free press as indispensable to democratic functioning, highlighting its role in enabling informed decision-making, citizen participation, and accountability of those in power. Without this freedom, the democratic process itself is seen as compromised”*

At the same time, a critical awareness arises that democracy cannot—and should not—regulate every aspect of individual life. Certain domains—especially those involving identity and bodily autonomy—must remain beyond the reach of majority rule.

Austria: [FG. 1] **P1:** *[I think] about the word democracy in a different way. So, for me, democracy would also mean voting on whether I can live out my life and my sexuality or whatever I want, so to speak. I don't really want that to be decided democratically. So, personal freedom, so to speak, is another thing that contrasts with democracy. Democracy means] that the group*

decides what applies to everyone or a majority decides what applies to everyone. But I don't want that in some areas of life”.

2. Representative system

The analysed materials reveal an ideal of democracy based mainly on two complementary dimensions. The first is that of collective decision-making, in which democracy is seen as the system in which the majority expresses the will of the people and determines common choices.

Ireland: [FG. 2] “the majority view dictates the ideology of the country and then we went down a little path as to what a true democracy was”.

The second is that of institutional representation, according to which the people exercise sovereignty indirectly, through rules, elections and representatives. In both visions, the democratic ideal is associated with participation, equality and respect for rules, and is recognised as a necessary principle for ensuring freedom and coexistence.

Italy: [Int. 16] “A: Sovereignty is managed indirectly by the people”.

France: [Int. 6] “PF: I would say that it is to guarantee that the citizens or the people of the State have the opportunity to make their voice and their wishes carried by an electoral method in what concerns governmental decisions and the evolution of the country, whether at the political, economic, cultural level, and that it is visible and audible from those in power and then again”.

3. People Power

A key dimension of the democratic ideal that emerged across countries is the notion of *people power*—the belief that citizens should have a meaningful and active role in shaping political decisions. This idea is rooted in the conviction that sovereignty ultimately belongs to the people, and that democracy must guarantee not only representation but also agency.

France: [Int. 11] “It is indeed a government or a mode of government of a country where the people have the decision. And then, it takes different forms. Me, before going to look for the definition, I was on... I hadn't put the word government back, I needed to refresh my memories anyway. But I was really already on... It's actually a... I had the word space, in my mind. A space where people, not to use citizens or people on purpose, but in any case, the people who live in this space say their opinion, participate more or less, very more or less actively in the decisions that impact this space. Spontaneously, what I would have said was that”.

For many participants, voting is seen as the most direct and tangible expression of this power. The act of choosing representatives or deciding on policies through elections is understood as a core democratic right, symbolising both individual autonomy and collective responsibility. However, there is also a widespread sense that participation should not be limited to the ballot box. People want to feel involved beyond periodic elections, through mechanisms that allow them to influence public debate, monitor decision-making, and hold institutions accountable.

Austria: [FG.1] *“P1: Also the opportunity to participate, so to speak. As an adult citizen, I have the right [to vote], others are excluded. That is less democratic, so to speak. There may be reasons why, for example, people who are too young or foreigners are excluded from voting. But I would tend to say that this is undemocratic. The more you allow people to participate, the more democratic it is. Especially the people who are affected by the things that are being voted on”.*

Poland: [FG.4] *“It is colloquially referred to as the rule of the people, right? Seemingly, we influence how this governance takes place. We discuss, we elect. And how it is in reality varies”.*

4. Community

The testimonies also express democracy as a lived practice rooted in everyday interactions—based on mutual listening, respect, and participation. Democracy is viewed as a space where everyone can freely express opinions, provided they do not infringe on others’ freedoms, adhering to the principle that “my freedom ends where yours begins.”

Czech: [FG.3] *“Participant 25: Well, to summarize, in the 1990s, everyone interpreted democracy and freedom in their own way and didn’t know the limits. Now, I think it’s much better because we’ve realized that freedom and democracy have limits. They start and end where the freedom and democracy of the other person begin. So, that’s how I would put it”.*

It is perceived as a balance between rights and duties, freedom and responsibility, requiring civic awareness and respect for rules. Democracy is possible only within a community that collectively recognizes itself, where no one is excluded, and differences—whether cultural, ideological, or individual—are embraced as essential to communal life.

Estonia: [FG.4] *“Participant A: Yes. I would add one thing. I wrote that ‘no one is left out’. One word that came to my mind is ‘compromise’. Democracy always means that you have different people, but there’s also the principle that they try to find an inclusive solution for everyone. So, I wrote that no one should be left out or feel that they’re not taken into consideration. That’s what should... should ideally be achieved”.*

5. Equality

Equality emerges as a foundational principle intertwined with the democratic ideal. Participants understand equality in multiple dimensions: equal rights, dignity, opportunities for participation, fairness, and inclusion. Democracy is associated with a system where everyone—regardless of social class, gender, origin, religion, or disability—holds equal value and the same opportunity to be heard. The right to vote frequently symbolizes this equality, as does the possibility to be elected, contribute to collective decisions, and live free from discrimination.

Portugal: [Int.7] *“Well, democracy for me is freedom. It’s discipline, it’s ideology. It’s recognising equality, in every expression. For me, democracy is respect for others. And equality isn’t it?”.*

Estonia: [FG.3] “Participant F: It’s about having freedom, equality, and opportunity. Everyone has the opportunity to run for office, vote, say what they like. Everyone is equal. And freedom is, I think, the most important one”.

Democracy ideal	
A lived and relational ideal	Democracy is not perceived merely as an institutional structure or a set of procedural rules, but as a concrete, everyday experience. It represents a symbolic and value-based horizon where individual rights, collective participation, and mutual recognition intersect.
Freedom as a fundamental pillar	Freedom is the most recurrent and widely shared value: freedom of expression, choice, movement, and self-determination. A particularly salient dimension is freedom of information, considered essential for enabling informed decision-making, critical participation, and holding power to account. At the same time, there is a clear sense that certain domains—especially those related to personal identity—must remain outside the reach of majority rule, safeguarding individual autonomy.
Representative and participatory democracy	Citizens value both the representative dimension of democracy (rules, elections, delegation) and the participatory one, which implies involvement beyond voting. The democratic ideal is one in which the people are active agents, not passive observers, and where sovereignty is exercised in a transparent, accessible, and accountable way.
Community and coexistence	Democracy is also experienced as a collective practice grounded in mutual listening, respect for rules, and inclusion of differences. The widely shared principle that “my freedom ends where yours begins” reflects a sense of shared boundaries and civic responsibility.
Equality as a transversal value	Finally, equality is a foundational element of the democratic ideal—equality in rights, dignity, access to opportunities, and the ability to be heard. Democracy is seen as a system where every person has equal value, regardless of background, gender, or status.

1.2 Democracy Opinion

When asked about their views on current democracy, participants provided a complex and nuanced set of reflections. While many expressed strong criticisms, others shared more neutral or conditionally positive perspectives. What emerges is not a binary picture, but a spectrum of experiences and opinions—ranging from disillusionment to cautious trust. To clarify the analysis, we present first the critical views, then the more positive ones, followed by an overall interpretation of the findings.

Critical Views on Democracy Today

The analysis of negative responses reveals a widespread sense of frustration and disappointment—not with democracy as an ideal, but with how it is currently functioning. Participants criticise both institutional structures and everyday political culture, highlighting five main areas of concern:

1. Distant, self-referential and ineffective politics

The most recurrent cluster relates to the perception of politics as distant, selfish and incapable of producing concrete results. The codes “Distant - selfish” and “No help for people” reflect a view of the political class as disconnected from the real needs of citizens, also confirmed by the frequent mention of “Broken promises”.

Ireland: [FG.3] *“our government. They say a lot but do nothing. And that’s our power, our Taoiseach [Irish Prime Minister] at the moment, he says a lot but has done nothing since. Like everyone in government, they promise a lot, and as I say, when you talk to anyone, any political person, ‘I’ll do my best’, and that’s their words to you, ‘I’ll do my best’, but I’ll do nothing in the end. That’s our society”.*

This distance also manifests itself in communication perceived as dysfunctional: “Disrespectful communication”, “Ineffective communication” and “No dialogue”, suggesting a political arena more oriented towards media conflict than public confrontation.

Poland: [FG.1] *“when it comes to the mistakes of politicians, I think everyone has also noticed that they also have such a great, developed ability to evade answering questions, or to answer diplomatically. (...) The person will start talking for an hour and a half, but the answer to the question was not there, so it is also I think that so the truth lies somewhere in the middle”.*

Codes such as “Fragmented parties”, “No ideals”, “No leadership” and “Unprepared” also point to a structural crisis of representation, with parties perceived as not very cohesive, lacking vision and dominated by contingent logics (The democratic structure remains, but the contents are emptied).

Germany: [FG.1] *“I have the feeling that politics or politicians don't really listen to experts, but rather make (um) money-driven decisions or business-oriented decisions that don't really correspond to the common good. And then also, if you look at it: who is sitting there? Who makes the decisions? Is it representative of the population? I think: No, it's not. And also, whether it makes sense for these people to make these decisions, because it's more about their own interests and not so much about those of minorities, right?”*

Czech: [FG.1] *“Participant 5: I miss a figure like Václav Havel. People with loving opinions—people you can listen to and take something from, apply it in daily life. When our politicians say something, it makes you feel sick. You can’t apply their words to your life, unlike Václav Havel, who could motivate you to improve yourself”.*

2. Mistrustful, disengaged and polarised citizens

Alongside institutional critique, participants also express concern about citizens’ disengagement. Apathy (*“Political disinterest”*, *“Lack of participation”*) and the erosion of political identity (*“Lack of political identity”*) are seen as contributing to a weak democratic culture.

Italy: [FG.2] *“P3 (M, 27): A few days ago, I was talking to someone who told me that he voted for X because his father told him to. I think this is serious. We are theoretically in a democracy, but we are shooting ourselves in the foot by doing this”.*

Czech: [FG.1] *“Participant 3: I feel like there’s also a lack of pride in being Czech. Many other nations take pride in who they are—they have something unique and show it to the world. But we don’t have that much. There’s nothing that makes us feel proud to live in the Czech Republic and say, “We have this or that, it’s beautiful here, and others don’t have it.” That’s missing for me”.*

Several responses highlight growing polarisation and social fragmentation, reflected in codes such as *“No mutual respect”*, *“Divided”*, and *“Controversial discussion”*. This points to a shift from healthy disagreement to antagonism.

Slovenia: [FG.1] *“Participant B: I, if I may just say this. I miss a little bit in Slovenia that people don’t speak up, go crazy for certain topics. But then, about everything else, they still I’ll give an example. I have a colleague with whom I agree on matters of daily politics on practically nothing. But he is my best friend. I can debate everything with him because we respect each other, because we say, look, this is what we agree on, let’s go for a beer together. We don’t talk about this and that. And we have a constructive debate about that. But in Slovenia, it is so much - ‘aha, you are left, I am right’. We don’t like each other. We can’t even play basketball together.” And that is sad”.*

3. Injustice and inequality perceptions

A third significant dimension emerging from the data concerns the widespread perception that democracy, in its current form, fails to guarantee fairness, equal representation, and social justice. Codes such as *“Inequality”*, *“Discrimination”*, and *“Elitism”* point to a disillusionment with democratic systems perceived as partial, exclusive, or indifferent to structural injustices.

For many participants, democracy does not sufficiently protect marginalized groups or uphold individual rights—particularly in the domains of civil liberties, gender equity, and minority protections.

Italy: [Int. 19] *“I think of this government and the decisions it makes, for example on civil rights, where the prime minister himself says that the family is only the traditional family, the family is father and mother – which, of course, is true, it is also that – but he does not take a position to guarantee the right freedoms. Or he is superficial on some points, such as the right to abortion, which is taboo with this government. It is full of pro-life associations”.*

Portugal: [Int.2] *“In Portugal, at this moment, being homosexual, for example, I feel that there are groups that can inhibit my freedom, and I think that no matter how much friction or sensitivity these groups might bring to our social and political landscape, as a minority—though it’s not a word I like, on the contrary—I feel that, for example, if I put myself in that position, yes, I fear that we might have a society that is less free in this sense. Another issue is the topic of women, the way women and their role in society are still viewed, this lack of equity and opportunities. The discrepancy that still exists between men and women in Portugal is alive”.*

Beyond these social concerns, there is a growing sense that democratic institutions are heavily influenced by powerful external actors, such as lobbies, corporations, and supranational entities, which undermines the idea of popular sovereignty and accountability.

Slovenia: [FG.1] *“I have read quite a lot of laws, and I dare to say, as an estimation, that there are at least 50 percents that are not in line with the Constitution. That means that somebody should go and clean it up.*

Moderator: In short, what is not working in our democracy could be said to be legislation.

Participant H: Legislation. Laws, yes”.

4. Disinformation, lack of education and the crisis of the public sphere

Another critical theme that emerges from the data is the crisis of the public sphere, shaped by the perceived manipulative power of the media and a lack of adequate political and media education. Codes such as “*Censorship*”, “*Disinformation*”, “*Ignorance*”, “*No political education*”, and “*No media education*” point to a widespread sense of disempowerment and frustration among citizens who feel unprepared to engage meaningfully with democratic processes.

Italy: [Int.5] *“Since this new government came into power, I think many things have changed. I see a desire to oppress certain groups and certain things, including through television and certain programmes. In my opinion, there has unfortunately been a clear change in recent times compared to how things were not so long ago, and I see this as something quite negative”.*

Czech: [FG.1] *“Participant 7: I think some people also abuse democracy by spreading misinformation and interpreting it as if they can say or claim whatever they want”.*

France: [FG.2] *“PC (M, 30): Politics is not included in school textbooks. Still today. We don't see it, there isn't a chapter in the story that says we're going to talk about politics”.*

Together, these insights point to a double deficit: a democratic system vulnerable to manipulation through media, and a citizenry insufficiently equipped to navigate or resist such dynamics. Addressing this gap in education and promoting transparency in information ecosystems appear crucial for restoring democratic legitimacy and empowering civic engagement.

5. Institutional system perceived as ineffective or in crisis

A final, recurring theme across national contexts is the perception that democratic institutions are ineffective, disconnected from citizens' needs, and unable to deliver on their promises. Codes such as “Low-turnout government”, “Constitution not respected”, and “Bureaucracy” highlight a shared sense of frustration and disillusionment with both the procedural and substantive dimensions of democratic life. Participants across countries denounce a gap between constitutional rights and their actual implementation:

Portugal: [FG.3] *“I believe that in the last, I suppose I'm not wrong, in our Constitution we have the right, the first right, to have a home, so from then on everything is wrong, everything is explained. In other words, the first right, which is the right to accommodation, health, education, and so on, is not guaranteed. And then I don't think there's any point in assigning more responsibility. We, as a society, as agents, I don't think we're participative enough, and then we blame the politicians. We say they don't do it. And what do we do? I'd go to the bar, and we'd say something bad. Okay, I think that's it... and I speak also against myself, I do that”.*

Italy: [Int.21] *“On paper it is one thing, but in real life it is another because not everyone votes, so there is a large proportion who abstain from voting and already there is no full right for the whole population, precisely because there are people who prefer not to give their opinion on a particular issue, which may be crucial for everyone. In Italian democracy, there are demands made by the people that need to be improved, especially in the areas of work and healthcare; there are issues that need to be addressed. On paper, the people want certain things, but in reality, there is not much response”.*

The crisis is twofold: on one side, procedural fatigue, where voting is perceived as increasingly symbolic and disconnected from real influence; on the other, substantive failure, where rights, services, and transparency are inconsistently upheld. Citizens describe a sense of powerlessness, where political participation seems ineffective and the democratic ideal remains unfulfilled.

France: [Int.5] *“PE: Well, actually, am I satisfied with it? No, I'm not satisfied because, from the voter's point of view, I find that we are atonic. I think we watch the trains go by. And from the point of view... So, I would enlarge, in fact, because, of course, when we return afterwards, we realize that democracy, in fact, from the point of view of the state level, we will say, ultimately, in fact, we can find... Finally, democracy is instilled, for example, in associations, etc. There are more and more associations with horizontal governance, blah blah blah, etc. So. Now, in fact, I find that, at the level of voters, we are not there. And at the level, in fact, of governance, we will say, at the level of the media, etc., it can also be complicated, with the concentration of the media,*

therefore freedom of the press and access to information, etc. And, indeed, a questioning, which can be increasingly greater, of the legitimacy of elected officials”.

Germany: [FG.1] “The bureaucracy is a central point that has bothered me several times. It simply takes too long. With the US elections, it's much worse now, but the country [Germany] is becoming more and more divided, and I hope that we can overcome this and sit down together again and find a good solution”.

Overall, the data reveal a widespread disconnect between democratic values and their concrete realization in institutional life. While the ideals of democracy are acknowledged, many participants feel that the current system lacks responsiveness, inclusiveness, and the capacity to ensure equal access to rights and services. This perception feeds into a broader narrative of democratic fatigue, where participation is seen as futile and institutions as increasingly distant from everyday realities.

Although quantitatively less frequent than negative opinions, **positive opinions** on democracy draw a picture characterised by appreciation for fundamental values, institutional functioning and improvements over the past or other contexts. These opinions show residual trust in a system perceived as imperfect, but still significant and improvable.

1. Functioning of democratic institutions

The most frequent code concerns the recognition of the functioning of the democratic system, also in its more procedural aspects. ‘Working system’ and ‘Electoral system’ express a certain degree of trust in institutions, in voting and in the capacity of democracy to guarantee alternation and representation. With respect to the first code, however, a feeling of relative trust should be emphasised, dictated by the fact that overall, the system works.

Czech: [FG.4] “Participant 30: I actually think that democracy in the Czech Republic is at a really good level. Even if we often don't like the outcomes of some processes, like elections, for example, we still have plenty of democratic tools that can be used. And it seems to me that, in the end, it works. So I think the level here is good.

Participant 38: I also think it's pretty good considering we've only had democracy for how long? 30 years since the regime change. And that has also impacted the thinking of the older generations, who don't see it that way. And then the younger ones might push the boundaries of what they can say or do. But I think 30 years is still a short time, and the system works quite well”.

Estonia: [Int.1] “Person L: I think it's pretty okay. I think we have democracy, because sometimes countries or governments claim that they have democracy but actually it's really biased or there's like a lot of bribing going on. I mean, of course, Estonia also has it, has the cases. But I think the situation is pretty okay. And thanks to that we have a democracy, people are more willing to go participate and make the change in the society”.

2. Freedom and fundamental rights

Another important core is “Freedom of speech”, which represents a pillar of democratic self-perception. The ability to freely express opinions, including critical ones, is seen as an achievement compared to authoritarian systems. Similarly, “Freedom to participate” and “Pluralism” refer to a vision of democracy as an open and pluralistic arena in which the diversity of opinions and cultures is welcomed and valued.

Austria: [FG.3] *“P10: I would say it is... Democratic participation is a given (...). There are elections. (um) Freedom of expression is also possible. In other words, there is a democratic space where you can move around, which also gives and confers anonymity. You can go and demonstrate. So, there are also surveys, and of course referendums. (um). Now everyone has to judge for themselves how far that should be expanded, but it's also there, so. (um) Yes, there are a lot of components that are good. But of course, there are also issues that could be developed further, I would say”.*

Slovenia: [FG.1] *“Participant B: The fact that we can talk freely and have different opinions is the charm of democracy”.*

3. Comparative and historical evaluations

A significant proportion of the positive codes express a relative and comparative, rather than an absolute, judgement. ‘Better than others’ and ‘Better than dictatorship’ place democracy on a scale of preferability to other political models or past eras. This type of evaluation is in line with the quote used very often by several respondents: “Democracy is the worst form of government, except for all the other forms that have been tried so far” (attributed to Churchill) and reflects an attitude of critical realism rather than enthusiasm.

Germany: [FG.3] *“And in my opinion, there is no alternative. It is simply the best state system. Unless it's a really good dictator who really means well with the people. (laughs) Then yes, I can imagine that it would work there too. [A dictator] who really approaches people and asks: Hey, what do you need? And that's how it should be: politics is actually meant for the people. And if a politician is a nice person, even if he is a dictator, and communicates with the people and implements it properly, I can also imagine that it would work. But I don't want Putin now”.*

Slovenia: [FG.4] *“Participant B: It's not perfect. But you don't have a better option”.*

4. Participatory and inclusive elements

Some positive codes emphasise participatory (“Citizens participation”) and inclusive (“Inclusion”, “Open-mindedness”) aspects, which can be read as signs of democratic vitality at the local or generational level.

Estonia: [FG.2] *“Participant H: Yes, I was thinking that we can assess democratic participation by voter turnout, which we've just recently been doing. So, the voter turnout, voter activity, I mean, is on the rise, and this reflects well how people feel their involvement and role in the democratic society”.*

Ireland: [FG.5] *“what I mean by that is, if it was majority only, we wouldn’t be looking at rights of LGBTQ or other minority groups. But in actual fact, I think our democracy does try to allow for that. So, I would say, minorities , yeah, I would settle for that”.*

5. Balanced and skeptical optimism

Finally, some codes such as “No corruption”, “Justice”, “Citizens help” and “Constructive skepticism” indicate the existence of spaces of good institutional functioning, civic will and administrative fairness. Although infrequent, these perspectives highlight that democracy is not entirely failing, but continues to operate in specific local, pragmatic, or selective contexts.

Germany: [FG.2] *“P2: At the end of the day, I would say that everything is still working well. I would say that it is democratic. I can't imagine that anything is corrupt in the elections or that something is being done that some people want, but that doesn't actually correspond to the truth. I would say that this is still the case in Germany”.*

France: [Int.5] *“PE: Besides, to finish answering you, is that for me, there is also a notion of responsibility. That is to say that democracy, in fact, all people have become responsible. It's not necessarily the great success, but in any case, there is this idea, in fact, behind the ambition. How do I find it in France? It's not... how should I put it? In fact, I don't know if my view, once again, is biased, but in any case, I think that we keep, in fact, a democratic shell which, sometimes, finds itself tinged with things which are not quite right. do. Namely, yes, of course, we have elections, we have free elections, multi-partyism, etc. Freedom of association and everything that goes with it. Now, that's all the thinking there is on the fifth republic, on the fact of being able to make decrees or hostile plans. We're here, it's not possible. This is the questioning that there was about police violence, about the fact of being able, as it has been the case many times, to be able to ban demonstrations. Prohibiting demonstrations because the police headquarters has decided that this or that demonstration cannot be held in public spaces, etc. I find and think that we must be extremely vigilant, and more and more so”.*

Positive opinions on current democracy outline a profile of conditional appreciation: citizens recognise the centrality of freedoms and rights, the functioning of institutions, the preferability of the democratic model, and glimpse spaces for openness and participation. However, this optimism is often measured, contextualised or linked to comparisons with worst-case scenarios. Democracy is thus advocated more as a value than as a fully satisfying experience.

In summary

Looking at the analysis of negative and positive opinions, we can paint a complex and multifaceted picture of public opinion regarding current democracy. These opinions do not polarise sharply into dichotomous views but are articulated along a continuum between critical disillusionment and conditional trust.

Democracy Opinion	
<p>A strongly critical and disenchanted perception prevails, as evidenced by the clear prevalence of negative codes</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Distance between citizens and politics, perceived as self-referential, corrupt, ineffective and incapable of representing real society. • Fragmentation, misinformation and lack of participation, which contribute to a feeling of civic disorientation. • Lack of trust in representative mechanisms and the media, with a strong emphasis on inequalities, elitism and a lack of civic-political education. • Disappointment with institutions, seen as non-transparent and unresponsive to citizens' needs.
<p>However, there are still positive aspects</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fundamental freedoms, such as freedom of speech and participation, recognised as intangible achievements of contemporary democracy. • Institutional functioning perceived as better than historical or international alternatives. • Pluralism, inclusion and openness, valued above all by groups that identify with local or generational dynamics. • Critical and informed participation of citizens.

Public opinion does not seem to reject democracy per se, but rather the way it is practised today. Much of the criticism is an expression of frustration with a betrayed ideal rather than a rejection of the ideal itself. **There is a sort of gap between normative democracy and empirical democracy.**

1.3 Democracy Expectations

The expectations emerging from the discussions do not point to a rejection of democracy as a model, but rather to a strong desire for its renewal, greater inclusiveness, and shared responsibility. People are not calling for a complete overhaul, but for improvements to make democratic systems more accessible, participatory, and responsive. Across countries, three main areas of concern stand out: active and informed participation, politics as a public service grounded in transparency and ethics, and clearer, more engaging communication. While a certain disillusionment with current practices is evident, what emerges more strongly is a sense of hope and belief in democracy's potential—if made more understandable, coherent, and humane.

1. Active and informed participation

One of the clearest demands emerging from participants is for stronger, more meaningful citizen participation. The desire for “more participation” is not limited to voting, but extends to the ability to influence decisions, engage in democratic processes, and understand their implications. This expectation is closely tied to the recognition that democracy requires preparation: **informed participation must be supported by a solid foundation of civic, political, and media education.**

Citizens express the need to be better equipped to interpret political messages, evaluate policy choices, and understand institutional mechanisms—especially in complex contexts such as European elections.

Austria: [FG.3] “R1: What would that be? What are topics that can be developed further?”

P10: Yes. Referendums, for example. More freedom of choice for citizens perhaps. (um). Participation opportunities, I say, to be able to decide on certain issues (um) and not always..., yes. You give your vote to someone, so to speak, but then they form a coalition and then it all becomes blurred again. And that's always, well not always... You don't always vote for what you actually get. So it somehow becomes blurred due to party politics”.

Italy: [Int. 18] “Since power belongs to the people, there should be ways to educate the people better, to put them in a position to have more in-depth knowledge, especially with regard to voting issues. For example, now that the European elections are coming up, the average voter does not know much about how the European Parliament works. Therefore, there should be ways to make voters aware of what they are going to vote for, to make voting more informed”.

2. Politics as a public service: ethics, transparency and listening

Participants expressed a clear expectation for politics to return to its core function: serving the public with honesty, transparency, and responsibility. People are not necessarily demanding a radical overhaul of the democratic system, but they are calling for greater coherence between promises and actions, clearer communication, and a more accessible and truthful political space.

Portugal: [Int.4] “Well, a space could be opened, for example, closer to election times, a space open to citizens, for instance. Of course, naturally regulated, with everything coordinated, etc. But it could possibly be an opportunity for citizens to speak. A space for citizens to have some contact with those who will represent them, for example. And, well, I think that with the reach that the media has, it could be something positive”.

Poland: [FG.1] “*To make democracy more transparent, that is, what I meant was that from the perspective of young people, what is happening at the European level, for example, or at the national level, is not so enticing, not so interesting and not worth paying attention to. And it seems to me that a lot could be done in this regard to encourage just participating or staying up to date even on such a local issue as micro*”.

These insights reflect a civic tension between skepticism and hope: while people are critical of current political practices, they believe in the potential for change—especially if institutions become more inclusive, proximate, and open to dialogue. Proposals like creating local spaces for public debate, bringing politics closer to daily life, and enhancing citizens' right to be informed at all stages demonstrate a concrete desire for a politics that listens, explains, and serves. Ultimately, the hope is for a form of democracy that is not only representative in form, but collaborative in practice.

France:[Int.1] “I think the legislative elections are very interesting. Afterwards, it would be necessary to develop local, regional or even municipal policy, to really raise desires. It would be really interesting”.

Italy: [Int.14] “*The interests of the population always come first. Rather than demonising your opponent or trying to destroy them, your goal should be to say, “I live in a wonderful country and I want it to be the best it can be”. Each of us can always improve. I see it here, in my own small way. The mayor is always doing something new and beautiful*”.

3. Better information

Several participants expressed the need for improved communication and access to political information, especially for younger generations. The existing modes of political messaging were often described as too heavy, inaccessible or overwhelming, which contributes to civic disengagement.

Italy: [Int.16] “*A: Lightness. Everything is always so heavy. The way they present things, if you watch a political party speaking, it's all very... there needs to be a little more lightness. It's complicated to say, we're talking about running a country and ideas, but there's a lack of lightness. It's always so heavy and suffocating that it makes you lose the will to go on*”.

Ireland: [FG.1] “*Speaker 6: Would there not be a chance that the Government could come up with an apparatus (app) to better inform young people or people in general and maybe there could be tighter laws against political violence, I'm just hoping the ball here (colloquialism: Hoping the ball is Irish slang for 'putting the idea to the group for discussion*].

Speaker F 2: I do believe they need a better platform to target young people, especially for things that challenge what you said challenge democracy, but if have no interest because it is just a bombarding of information when it comes to local elections, and they (the Government) are not targeting the information correctly towards people”.

Beyond the technical or digital aspects, these reflections often converge with a deeper call for a renewed civic spirit based on empathy, shared responsibility and the common good. Participants across various countries linked access to meaningful information with the ability to act not only for individual interests, but for the well-being of others. Whether speaking of local mayors improving community services, or lamenting the erosion of values like equality and care in the public sphere, these voices stress that democracy requires more than access to information—it needs a cultural framework that encourages solidarity, dialogue and ethical commitment.

Portugal: [FG.3] *“I think we could be more empathetic and more collaborative. Information, and to mention my colleague a bit, certain helps exist, for example, that people don't exactly know about, but no one gives them that knowledge either. And I think we should be a bit more... less selfish. And that makes each person's role in society a little bit more important, we could all contribute to each other, we could provide information”.*

Slovenia: [FG.4] *“Participant D: I would agree with Participant C. There will always be media. If nothing else, they will be paid to talk and to inform us. They will be somebody's voice. Unless they stand up against the system and say they will not work like that anymore. I hope to see more of that”.*

Citizen’s expectations outline a vision of democracy not as a structure to be dismantled, but as a living system in need of care and reform. Their suggestions are not abstract or utopian, but concrete and actionable, aimed at restoring trust and encouraging a more meaningful connection between citizens and institutions. This renewed democratic vision is built on three core pillars:

- **Civic education and informed participation**, including through more effective media tools;
- **Public ethics and institutional transparency**, with consistency between political promises and action;
- **Inclusion, representation, and responsiveness to local communities.**

Rather than a list of complaints, these reflections represent a collective call to action—an invitation to rethink democracy as a shared, everyday practice, capable of addressing contemporary challenges and rebuilding public confidence through openness, integrity, and proximity.

1.4 Democracy Threats

Opinions show a strong awareness of internal tensions and external pressures that threaten democratic stability.

1. Extremism and the decline of civic values

Among the concerns raised by participants, one of the most prominent is the rise of extremism, mentioned across multiple countries and linked to increasing polarisation, aggressive discourse, and anti-democratic tendencies. The fear is not limited to a particular ideology but reflects a broader anxiety about the destabilising effects of political extremes—both on public debate and on democratic institutions themselves.

Beyond the political sphere, participants also point to a deeper, more diffuse erosion of civic culture. Through references to concepts like *drift in values*, *aggressiveness*, *lack of respect*, *loss of cohesion*, and *superficiality*, they highlight a perceived decline in the shared democratic norms and values that underpin civil coexistence. The difficulty of holding constructive conversations, the tendency to prioritise controversy over dialogue, and a general weakening of mutual respect are seen as symptomatic of a society where the fabric of democratic life is fraying.

France: [Int.1] “PA: What is quite worrying at the moment is the weight of the extreme right, in particular. Extremes in general, because when a country and its people go towards extremes, it is not necessarily a good sign. So afterwards, we talked a lot about the far right and the far left. Personally, I am not convinced that the left of the current popular bridge (Nouveau Front Populaire) that we had in the legislative elections is extreme. Now, indeed, if people think that this is extreme, perhaps we need to reframe the debate and redefine the institutions a little so that people can express themselves freely. But in any case, today, what would be interesting is to perhaps give more weight to popular speech, since that is what is being asked for through the various elections. Because we know very well that the far right is quite populist. And then the far left, on the other hand, also relies on popular demands”.

Poland:[FG.1] “It seems to me that as far as my answer is concerned, but I think this also shines through in other answers... that very often also in the media, but also between people - it is very difficult to talk to each other and there is no such culture of discussion and very often people just want to express the most controversial opinions”.

2. Social Media & Disinformation

Digital media emerge as a double-edged sword in participants’ reflections: on one hand, they offer unprecedented access to information; on the other, they are widely seen as channels for disinformation and manipulation. Social media platforms, in particular, are frequently mentioned as spaces where falsehoods spread rapidly, where communication can be deliberately distorted, and where media ownership and censorship raise concerns about the integrity and diversity of information.

Participants highlight how manipulated media contribute to deepening societal divisions, fostering prejudices, and triggering social unrest, such as protests and riots fueled by misinformation. There is a widespread sense that democracy itself is under threat from these dynamics, as coordinated online campaigns, especially by far-right groups, actively seek to undermine public trust in democratic institutions. The abundance of media options allows individuals to selectively consume content that reinforces their own views, which further fragments public discourse and erodes mutual understanding.

France: [FG.2] “PE (M, 19): [the media and social networks] It creates a big influence on the people. And in fact, that gives rise to prejudices. And so these prejudices will create problems, and therefore will create demonstrations and riots. Like for example racism among young people, which is becoming more and more popular. And so it's because of that that, for example, riots, for example in 2023, take place. Or other protests even earlier”.

Portugal: [Int.1] “And this democracy, I see it threatened every day by social media. That is, the proliferation of fake news. Today, we risk going to bed in a democracy and waking up in a dictatorship because we see that far-right parties are very well organized on social media. They have digital soldiers, and what has been observed is a constant attack on the pillars of our democratic institutions, attempting to discredit them, attempting to undermine public trust in democratic institutions”.

Estonia: [FG.2] “That’s the danger we have with the abundance of media opportunities nowadays. People follow what is most suitable for them, perhaps, without thinking twice about whether it presents the whole truth. And then you get the feeling that everyone who thinks differently doesn’t understand a thing and is hopelessly lost”.

3. Institutional Fragility

This theme reflects growing concern about a crisis of democratic participation and a weakening connection between institutions and citizens. Codes such as *abstentionism*, *passive participation*, *denial voting*, and *lack of listening* point to a perceived erosion of civic engagement and a widespread sense of being unheard by political actors. People express frustration at the ineffectiveness of their participation—whether through voting or protest—and the impression that their voices have little real impact on institutional decisions.

Participants also raise deeper doubts about the resilience of democratic systems themselves, noting signs of structural instability and institutional inadequacy, particularly in relation to public services like welfare. In this view, democracy is seen as something fragile, constantly under pressure and requiring continual reinforcement—through inclusion, open dialogue, and respect for diverse perspectives.

France: [FG.3] “So, the lack of listening. People are taking to the streets, making demands, and we really have the impression that they are just blows in the water, that no one is listening to them. It still has a bit of a discouraging side”.

Ireland: [FG.1] “Speaker M 6: 05:23 I would be of the opinion that democracy is always under threat, always a work in progress, when you look back at the to the founding of America, they did

not know what they were doing, they were constantly working on it (democracy). I would say we need always to strengthen our democracy by allowing people to have different opinions and respecting them and allowing that the whole point of the discussion process and discussion is the main tenant of democracy in the beginning”.

Far from being indifferent, participants demonstrate a sharp awareness of the many forces—both internal and external—that threaten democratic stability. The rise of extremism and the erosion of shared civic values are seen as warning signs of a society drifting away from constructive dialogue and mutual respect. This deterioration is not only ideological but cultural, affecting the tone and quality of everyday democratic life.

At the same time, digital media—while offering opportunities for information and engagement—are largely viewed with suspicion. They are perceived as amplifiers of disinformation, manipulation, and polarisation, contributing to a fragmented public sphere in which shared facts and common ground become harder to find. These dynamics are seen as particularly dangerous when exploited by actors seeking to undermine democratic institutions from within.

Finally, the crisis of participation—manifested in apathy, protest fatigue, and widespread mistrust of political institutions—reveals a deep disconnect between citizens and those meant to represent them. While democracy is often described as a work in progress, participants fear that its foundations are being weakened by inaction, exclusion, and institutional inertia.

Taken together, these concerns express a form of *critical loyalty*: a belief that democracy is still worth defending, but only if it evolves. People are not asking for perfection, but for a system that listens, includes, and reflects the values it claims to uphold. In their critiques lies not only frustration—but also the hope that renewal is still possible.

In summary

EXPECTATIONS	THREATS
<p>1. Active and informed participation Desire for deeper involvement in decision-making, supported by civic and political education.</p>	<p>1. Institutional fragility Low participation, abstention, and the sense that citizens are unheard by institutions.</p>
<p>2. Politics as public service Call for honesty, transparency, and ethics in politics; coherence between words and actions.</p>	<p>2. Decline of civic values & extremism Rising polarization, aggressiveness, disrespect, and erosion of democratic norms.</p>
<p>3. Better information Request for clear, accessible communication and targeted outreach, especially to younger generations.</p>	<p>3. Disinformation & social media manipulation Spread of fake news, echo chambers, and distrust fueled by digital platforms.</p>
<p>4. Inclusion & proximity Hope for institutions that are close to citizens, open to dialogue, and responsive to local needs.</p>	<p>4. Disconnect between citizens and institutions Frustration with unkept promises, distant politics, and lack of listening.</p>
<p>5. Education for democracy People want tools to better understand, evaluate, and engage in political life.</p>	<p>5. Cultural erosion of dialogue Breakdown in respectful conversation and shared understanding in public discourse.</p>

1.5 Democracy Trust & Distrust

A big part of people's trust comes from the intrinsic value of the democratic system, pointing out that many people still believe in democracy as a principle. This is backed up by comparisons with other political systems, which reinforce the idea that democracy is seen as the least bad option, an imperfect system but better than any authoritarian alternative. The comparison with authoritarian regimes therefore fuels a defensive trust, based on a collective or cultural memory of worse alternatives.

Czech: [FG.3] “Participant 23: It’s something different to have trust in the government and trust in the system. And in democracy, definitely yes”.

Italy: [Int.20] “I am confident in the sense that I hope we will not return to dictatorial times, and in this sense I feel protected by the Constitution. However, it is not that I have so much confidence in our politicians”.

1) Guarantee institutions and instruments

Despite general disillusionment with politics, many participants still express trust in core democratic institutions such as the electoral system, the constitution, the judiciary, and supranational structures like the EU. These are seen as essential safeguards that uphold democratic order even when political actors fail.

Czech: [FG.2] “Participant 19: I see the guarantee of democracy primarily in the European Union because for me, some of the political parties are more like a theater, the system itself, but the fact that we’re anchored in the European Union and that we adopt the vast majority of our legislation from the EU is, for me, the basis of democracy. That’s the foundation for me”.

Germany: [FG.3] “P1: I think electoral law, our electoral law, works so far. Well, if you compare that... Well, it's also the case, really, um, yes, that there isn't as much manipulation as in some other countries. Well, at least I hope so, or I have the impression that our elections aren't rigged like that. And I think that's really important, because you don't need elections if they're pointless anyway because of bribes and the like”.

2) Residual Trust and Hope

A form of subtle, sometimes irrational trust still emerges across several interviews — not rooted in institutions, but in personal impressions, emotional intuition, and a hope for change. This trust is often directed at individuals perceived as credible or morally close, rather than at the political system as a whole.

Germany: [FG.4] “P6: So, it's always this trust in an institution. Yes, the idea may be good, but there are also people at the levers. And whether I trust every single person in a higher position... That's another question”.

Estonia: [Int.A] “I have some people I trust, but they are people who are in politics and who are also good acquaintances of mine. So I know them as people. I know what their values are. I know that they are, if not in some scene themselves, at least good allies. But above that. I don't know, I don't exist for them”.

Italy: [FG.2] “P3(M,27) For me, trust is important, how much the person speaking conveys it to you. We are used to seeing lots of people talking and making propaganda. Everyone has great ideas during election campaigns, but if the person speaking doesn't convey trust to you on a gut level, or maybe they've been in politics for 10 years and have always failed, I don't trust them again”.

3. Shared Ideals and Proximity

Participants express a notable shift in trust — away from institutional representatives and toward ordinary citizens. This confidence is increasingly rooted in personal experiences of integrity, common sense, and rationality, rather than in a generalized trust in formal institutions. Trust is not reserved only for large-scale democratic structures, but also extends to interpersonal and political relationships that are perceived as close, relatable, and trustworthy.

France: [Int.2] *“Afterwards I also think that I also have confidence in democracy, in the sense that I still have enough confidence in the citizens, in the French people, and I think that if it has been threatened, I think that we would still be able to manifest itself so that it does not disappear, or that it is not altered, and as such, I think that democracy is still something in which we can have more or less confidence, but to say that we have complete confidence”.*

Portugal: [FG.1] *“With regard to trust, I'm always going to trust in one way or another, that is, I'm going to give credit because we believe, I believe in the potential of human beings to do fantastic things. This trust doesn't go away, regardless of the regime we're living under, in our case, democracy. But I continue to trust because I have a strong belief in the ability of human beings to overthrow anything and to go and move towards a greater good. I think that's my confidence, a greater good”.*

Looking at the data, distrust in democracy seems to be a complex issue with different layers: political, institutional, informational, and cultural.

1) Politics as main source of disillusionment

The most significant component of mistrust is concentrated on politics. The codes “*Broken promises*”, “*Disinterest in people*” and “*Corruption*” highlight how the political class is perceived as unreliable, distant and self-referential.

Czech: [FG.1] *“Participant 7: I think that when people vote, they can end up disappointed with the politicians they chose. The politicians promise something and then don't fulfill it, which discourages people from voting again. I think it's good when someone completely new comes into politics, someone who isn't tainted by politics, because people might trust them more than politicians who promise things and then do nothing”.*

This view fits perfectly into the context of the crisis of representation, where the substance of political participation and responsibility is being hollowed out. Voters therefore continue to vote, but feel that their choices do not bring about real change (“*No real changes*”, “*Instability*”).

Slovenia: [FG.2] *“Participant A: You try what's best. But then they [individual parties] realise that they can't do anything on their own. And then they go and get a coalition. And you realise that there is no change. One's got the majority. But not strong enough to do something on their own. Anywhere”.*

Furthermore, codes such as “No accountability”, “No common perspectives”, and “Too many alliances” show an opinion that politics lacks consistency and accountability, weakening the trust between politicians and citizens. This leads to a feeling that no one pays the price for political mistakes, contributing to systemic distrust.

Italy: [Int.32] *“We criticise the government, but you never know what's behind it, because there are things going on inside, things between them that we could never know, that they haven't even told us about. Maybe they know that in a week's time a nuclear bomb is going to drop and we don't. For example, these are their secrets, which we will never know. So there really is a wall, in the sense that politics... Their communication is advertising”.*

Czech: [FG.2] *“Participant 12: I don't know, like from the recent years, with the parliamentary elections, I'm not sure about trust because there are parties in the government now that wouldn't have made it if they hadn't formed the five-party coalition. So, I'm not sure if that's democratic”.*

2. Discouraged and powerless citizens

The code ‘No citizens power’, along with ‘Citizens disinterest’, ‘Abstentionism’ points to a perceived disconnection between citizens and the democratic system. This mistrust often manifests as political apathy and low participation, reinforcing a vicious cycle of disengagement and apathy.

Portugal: [FG.4] *“I feel that with certain other organizations you mentioned, like unions and those kinds of groups, I sometimes lose a bit of trust, because I feel that many movements try and do a lot, but the response is often inaction, and not much ends up happening. So, I lose a bit of faith in the government's response to the population's discontent. But in democracy itself, I still have some trust, it's still there”.*

Italy: [Int.21] *“At the moment, I don't have much confidence, because if even the people who go out to vote don't believe in it and abstain, I could never trust it. I don't see a coalition today, a coming together to fight for the issues that are important to us”.*

3. The ambivalent role of the media

As emerges from citizens' reports in different countries, the spread of disinformation raises doubts about the reliability of the news: one person in Estonia admits that they cannot fully trust the democratic system precisely because it is impossible to verify the reliability of information; in Italy, criticism focuses on the role of politicians and journalists, who are perceived as responsible for the deterioration of public debate; while in the Czech Republic, there is frustration at the evident bias of the media, which negatively influences the perception of political issues.

These experiences show that, although the role of the media is crucial for democracy, it is often ambivalent: on the one hand, it can promote participation and information, but on the other, it risks fuelling divisions and mistrust, hindering the functioning of a healthy and inclusive democratic debate.

Estonia: [Int.C] *“Q: Do you trust the democratic system in Estonia?”*

Person D: No, I can't say I trust it one hundred percent. Again, I could say that so and so, that fifty percent I trust, fifty percent I would rather not.

Q: What influences your trust one way or the other?

Person D: Trust is definitely affected by the fact that a lot of this kind of misinformation is spread. That I can't be sure about the information that is shown to me, whether it is right or wrong”.

Czech: [FG.4] *“When the moderator is obviously biased towards someone from an independent perspective, I always try to look at it objectively, whether I like the person or not. Whether it's this side or that side, sometimes it's obvious that the moderator is on one side. And that bothers me because I can see how it influences people around me. And when you actually look up the information on what was discussed, you find out that in reality, it's different. So that's probably it for me”.*

4. General crisis and legitimacy

A few unusual but significant codes, such as “No future”, “Covid”, “Populism” and “EU”, refer to recent events or global trends that have contributed to further eroding trust in democratic institutions. The reference to “Covid” can be interpreted as a moment of rupture, while “Populism” and “EU” refer to tensions between the national and supranational dimensions, between representation and sovereignty.

France: [Int.11] *“PK: it was shaken around Covid. When I saw a form of... When I saw decisions made that, for me, would have deserved to be discussed, so there, more than ever, I found that it... Well, I'm going to be very clear, for me, I'm very much into controlling emotions, but in the sense of managing emotions, the meaning of the messages, the emotions behind them, that. And so, I really had the impression of being manipulated by fear. And fear, I see it, in fact, in society”.*

Czech: [FG.1] *“Participant 3: For me, when I see how easily people fall for populist opinions, I lose faith in democracy”.*

Germany: [FG.1] *“Okay. In principle, I also have confidence in the function that it [the democratic system] currently fulfils. If I can roughly agree with both of them. Apart from our bureaucracy, which is always very cumbersome. Unfortunately, I also have no confidence that really complex problems, such as the climate crisis, can be solved in the long term. Unfortunately, I have completely lost faith in that. On the one hand, in terms of German democracy. I'm completely ignoring the fact that this is an even bigger challenge globally. But I don't believe that we alone can achieve certain goals, such as the utopian 1.5-degree target or something like that... The only thing we can do as Germany is something that I no longer have any confidence in politics, or in our democracy or our performance”.*

MEDIA'S ROLE IN DEMOCRACY

Note on interpretation

In analysing participants' views, the concept of *media* has been intentionally interpreted in a broad sense, encompassing both media actors (such as journalists and news organisations) and media platforms (such as social networks and digital information channels). This inclusive approach reflects the way participants themselves referred to “the media”, often without a clear distinction between these dimensions. As a result, the roles and expectations described in this section refer to both the professional practices of those who produce news and the structural or technological features of the media environment in which that news is consumed.

2.1 Idea of Media's Role in democracy

The most evident demand expressed concerns the need for impartiality and accurate information. Participants emphasized that the media should remain neutral, free from political or economic interference, and committed to delivering reliable and comprehensive facts. Equally important is the clear distinction between opinion and factual reporting, ensuring that audiences can trust the information they receive.

Czech: [FG.1] “Participant 2: I think the role of the media should be to aggregate all that information, as Participant 8 mentioned, summarizing what has been promised and what has been fulfilled, without saying whether it was good or bad—just present the information and let people decide for themselves. It should be mostly objective”.

France: [Int.1] “for me, the media must have a neutral role. They must not fuel gossip and make things worse. They must have a role as journalists to ask questions that are fair on the subject. I have the impression that the media direct thinking according to their own point of view. And often, I change radio stations, precisely, because I feel the journalist's personal opinion on the subject”.

1) The traditional watchdog

A particularly valued role attributed to the media is that of holding those in power accountable. The *watchdog* function—frequently mentioned—highlights the expectation that the media actively scrutinize political institutions, uncovering cases of abuse, corruption, or dysfunction. This oversight is widely seen as a fundamental pillar of democratic life, essential for promoting transparency and ensuring that institutions remain answerable to the public.

Germany: [FG.1] “**P4:** The media can put pressure on politicians faster than individual citizens and spread the word quickly”.

Italy: The media enable us to understand whether someone is saying the right things or saying things that are inappropriate.

2. Media as education

A segment of the public also assigns an important educational role to the media. This includes supporting political education by helping citizens understand democratic processes, as well as promoting critical thinking—an increasingly necessary skill in the face of information overload.

Portugal: [Int.7] *“The media basically has an obligation to educate”.*

Italy: [Int.23] *“They should provide food for thought so that the person hearing it starts to think and seeks further information to form their own idea and opinion”.*

3. Pluralism and social Cohesion

In addition to this, the media are expected to act as a voice for the people and for pluralism, by representing diverse and minority perspectives. Some participants highlighted the media’s potential to foster a sense of community, thus contributing to greater social cohesion.

France: [Int.2] *“PB: The role of the media and if, therefore, we also include social networks, I think it is very, very important. It's inevitable. Firstly, I think it is still important that the media respect a certain pluralism, in any case, that we hear a little bit of everything, which has not necessarily always, I have the impression, been the case”.*

Estonia: [Int.N] *“I think, responsibility of media in Estonia should be controlling the echo chambers, controlling the polarization, controlling the algorithm of social media by showing you your own views which you already have, and reinforcing your previous beliefs. This is a problem everywhere. I think so in Europe that the echo chamber is polarizing. And I think so the role of media should be encouraging people to participate more in any of the thing that is for the betterment of the country. And not a single party, not a single group voicing for the ordinary people, the voices of the ordinary locals and the citizens should be heard, whether it's expats or not”.*

4. Independence, neutrality & professionalism

Finally, several reflections highlight the structural conditions necessary for the media to effectively fulfill these roles. Independence, political neutrality, and a high standard of professionalism are seen as essential prerequisites. Above all, media freedom is regarded as a non-negotiable condition for ensuring that the media can operate with integrity and serve the public interest.

Poland: [FG.4] *“A journalist must have knowledge, well, it is impossible to write a good article without it, or to convey information clearly, if there is no knowledge of the subject, proper education. Education of some sort, it doesn't have to be specifically directional, but well, some kind of knowledge simply must have”.*

Italy: [Int.27] (Journalists) *They should be people outside politics.*

Media's role Idea	
Impartiality and Accuracy	Media should provide neutral, unbiased, and accurate information, clearly distinguishing facts from opinions to build audience trust.
Watchdog Role	Media are expected to hold political power accountable by exposing corruption, abuses, and dysfunctions, supporting transparency.
Educational Function	Media have a role in educating citizens about democratic processes and promoting critical thinking to navigate information overload.
Pluralism and Social Cohesion	Media should represent diverse voices, including minorities, fostering pluralism and a sense of community to enhance social cohesion.
Independence and Professionalism	Media must be independent from political and economic pressures, politically neutral, and staffed by knowledgeable, professional journalists to maintain integrity.

2.2 Opinion Media's role in democracy

A widespread dissatisfaction emerged regarding the current state of the media and their role in democratic life. The most frequently reported problem concerns a perceived lack of impartiality and objectivity. This is closely followed by concerns about unreliability and misinformation, with participants referring to manipulation, contradictions, and the absence of credible sources. Such views reflect not only a general crisis of trust, but also a deeper perception of information being strategically used, rather than serving the public good.

Czech: [FG.3] “Participant 22: We know that the media isn’t independent. They belong to someone. Of course. And that person lobbies for certain people or parties. The media will never be the way it should be”.

Many participants expressed frustration with what they see as external pressures—particularly economic and political—that compromise the integrity of the media system. Strong criticism was directed at corporate control and profit-driven logics, such as clickbait practices, which are believed to degrade the quality of information and distort editorial priorities.

Italy: [Int.12] “Unfortunately, with the advent of social media, newspapers have also changed. They seek likes and views. They post useless news on Facebook, such as “today this actor went

to the bathroom three times”, which is of no interest to us. But all it takes is for someone to click on that newspaper headline and the views and ads roll in. Google advertising pays them accordingly, so they try to get paid by advertising rather than real news”.

Additionally, the precarious working conditions of journalists were seen as contributing to superficial reporting and limited independence. These concerns cast doubt on the structural neutrality of the media and on their ability to fulfil a true public service function.

Slovenia: [FG.1] *“A journalist is also a human being and on a payroll and is afraid, even more so in the case of private media, of being fired. At RTV, practically no one has been sacked, although one was reporting on Gaza from Singapore. Or from Bangkok.*

Participant B: There's more. Not that one will be fired. Most journalists in private media are not even employed. They are self-employed entrepreneurs [note: journalists in private media are often forced to take a status of self-employed entrepreneur]. And if something is not right with the owners or editors, they just say good bye”.

1. Format and Quality of content

Criticism also focused on the formats and overall quality of content. Participants described the media landscape as saturated with low-quality programming: superficial news, sensationalist guests, poorly moderated debates, and repetitive or unengaging formats. Traditional television, in particular, was singled out as emblematic of this decline, associated with outdated storytelling, populist tones, and entertainment-driven approaches. In contrast, there was a clear and consistent demand for more in-depth, accessible, and well-structured information—something that many felt is currently lacking.

Italy: *If I turn on the TV and there are harmful programmes that are objectively bad, that's how people grow up.*

Portugal: [FG.2] *“I get fed up watching the news and videos and everything else, because what I see is attacks on each other, and that's what it comes down to for me, for example, for me, if I'm a winner, I'm not going to say that other people's products are worse than mine, I'm going to say that mine is better than theirs, and they're always attacking, always... We're not like them, they want to do this and then they'll do that. And these attacks, no, no, they don't mean anything to me. I want to know what they're going to do to move forward”.*

Poland: [FG.2] *“in our opinion, the stability of democracy in the context of the media is certainly undermined by the lack of professionalism of journalists. Then, there is a lot of information and there is a problem with checking whether it is credible or not. You also have to put a lot of your own energy into it. And there are no such safe places to verify it. There are also no trusted sources, but if you want to check some information, to be sure, you have to look for it yourself in many, many sources”.*

2. Social and Digital Media

The negative impact of digital media, especially social platforms, was another recurring theme. Social media were frequently associated with echo chambers, polarising algorithms, fake news, hate speech,

and addictive behaviours. Participants expressed concern that the digital environment amplifies the flaws of the broader information ecosystem, deepening divisions and undermining the possibility of a constructive public discourse.

France: [FG.2] “PE (M, 19): *In networks, there is an algorithm. And so, in relation to sensitive information or precise information that you defend, it will lead to certain parties. So ultimately, you're going to like a party more, precisely, because you only liked one thing about the party. And so, little by little, with the algorithm, it will only give you things that will be in favor of that party. And so, your idea will be completely distorted*”.

Germany: [FG.2] “P1: *I would put everything in the social media sector at the very, very bottom of the list in terms of media quality. We're often somehow caught up in a bubble. For example, if you realize: I'm interested in AfD topics, then I only get AfD topics. That's why a medium like a printed newspaper or something like that is somehow better, because in the end a wide range of opinions are presented. And the newspaper doesn't know [what interests me]*”.

Portugal: [FG.3] “*The internet has a problem, which is the disinformation that seems to appear right away*”.

3. Censorship & Exclusion

Another area of concern relates to issues of *censorship, exclusion, and representational imbalance*. Several participants referred to both public and private media as engaging in forms of censorship, while many felt that ordinary citizens are rarely given a voice. The invisibility of minorities, and a perceived lack of attention to people's real problems, reinforced the sense that the media often fail to represent society in all its complexity.

Italy: [Int.29] “A: *Before, when there weren't these differences between channels, or rather there weren't such big differences between Rai channels and other channels like La 7, recently there's been a clear difference, in my opinion, in that various things have been censored on Rai channels and so, in my opinion, information is no longer as “free” as it was before, it's very guided. In short, in my opinion, even with regard to newspapers, i.e. what news to report and how to report it, everything is quite guided, in my opinion, unlike other channels*”.

Slovenia: [FG.2] “Participant E: *Even if there are those who dare to say something outside, so that they don't obey, either they are removed to another news slot or back to the office*”.

Estonia: [Int.1] “Person L: *Yeah, it's not really democracy when you're limiting your journalists on what they want to post about. And if it especially if it was against EKRE. Then I read that it was definitely like censored somehow, or they did, or the editor didn't, the main editor didn't let it go through*”.

4. Too negative news

Many European citizens perceive the media as overly focused on negative news, which leads to anxiety, emotional fatigue, and, in some cases, a conscious withdrawal from traditional news sources. This constant exposure to negativity is often seen as a commercial strategy aimed at "selling" fear and shock, contributing to a decline in trust—especially in sensationalist outlets. As a result, people increasingly choose to limit their news consumption or turn to lighter, alternative platforms. There is a strong desire for more balanced reporting that also includes positive and constructive stories, along with a clear need to find a healthy balance between staying informed and protecting one's mental well-being.

Czech: [FG.1] *“Participant 5: For me, it's what happens in the world that affects how I feel or why I'm sometimes negative. When you constantly hear about climate change, the war in Ukraine, COVID, and how resources are running out, you start to feel that things aren't like they used to be. Just ten years ago, things were different, but now we have COVID, the war in Ukraine, and alarming climate issues. It feels like too much information sometimes”.*

Ireland: [FG.3] *“you look at the news now, and there's nothing in the news only bad, you know”.*

Slovenia: [FG.1] *“we Slovenians are not only sensationalists, but negative sensationalists. And here we should follow the Croatians a little bit more and emphasise the positive things a little bit more. But we are not able to do that”.*

European citizens expressed deep concern about the current state of the media and its ability to serve democracy. The perceived lack of impartiality, the spread of misinformation, and the prioritisation of commercial and political interests over public service have collectively contributed to a growing crisis of trust. Citizens feel overwhelmed by low-quality content, sensationalism, and negativity—factors that not only distort public discourse but also alienate audiences from the media altogether.

Digital platforms, while offering broader access, are often seen as amplifying these problems through polarising algorithms and disinformation. At the same time, concerns about censorship, underrepresentation, and the invisibility of ordinary voices highlight a growing disconnect between media narratives and the lived realities of citizens. What emerges is a widespread desire for a media system that is more balanced, inclusive, independent, and ultimately more aligned with democratic values.

Despite the widespread criticism of the current media landscape, participants also acknowledged a number of **positive aspects** and potential strengths within the media system—especially when it comes to their civic role, digital adaptability, and capacity for public service. While trust remains cautious and conditional, it is not absent. Citizens do not reject the role of the media outright; rather, they express hope for a more transparent, inclusive, and democratically engaged information environment.

1. Social media

Social media were frequently mentioned as powerful tools for rapid access to information and for reaching younger audiences. Participants appreciated their immediacy and ability to facilitate the circulation of ideas and public expression.

Austria: *I think that shorter videos in simple language are perhaps a bit more conducive to democracy, because more people are then picked up by perhaps really short and simple information.*

Germany: *I think that's another good thing about social media, that individuals or journalists also have a platform. That wasn't the case 20 years ago, when nobody had the opportunity to put forward their own opinion. Just as a private individual or even as a small journalist, you always had to talk about... There were only big discussion panels, like on TV on a Tuesday evening or something. That's a huge advantage. The only thing I [like] about print media is that the seriousness of the information is often relatively high, I would say, compared to what someone claims on social media. It doesn't have to be, but it can be.*

2. Public Media

While not immune from criticism, public service broadcasters were often seen in a more favourable light compared to private or commercial outlets. Some participants perceived them as more neutral, balanced, and trustworthy, especially when operating under clear public interest mandates and regulatory oversight. Concepts such as impartiality and objectivity were frequently mentioned—not only as positive values, but also as aspirations that public media could (and should) uphold more consistently.

Slovenia: [FG.3] “Participant G: I find RTV quite objective. I find it maybe a little bit more left-leaning, but I still find it quite objective”.

Estonia: [Int.K] “overall, Estonia is very, is very like, very good. Yeah, especially the state media, because the state media doesn't speak about gossip or so. For me, that's the best you could get, because they don't, yeah, they don't really speak about gossip or too much about sport, which I don't care so much. They have just clear information”.

3. Civic role: participation, support, awareness

Although rarely, participants also recognised the civic role of the media in promoting democratic engagement. Media were valued when they:

- facilitated public debate,
- supported citizen awareness and action (e.g. during elections or public campaigns),
- and helped individuals make informed decisions.

In this regard, media are seen not only as sources of information but also as tools for *education, empowerment, and active citizenship*.

Italy: [Int.11] *“Those online and on Facebook are a bit like those on TV. If they are newspaper articles, such as La Repubblica, they are shown as they want them to be. I see the difference more when I follow and watch a programme where people can talk and give their opinion, whether positive or negative. Because at that point there is no filter and there is someone who has the ability to say what they really think and no one interrupts them”.*

Slovenia: [FG.1] *“Moderator [sees Participant F nodding in agreement]: Participant F, would you also turn to journalists if you found yourself in such distressful situation? And you would still have the impression that if you tell a journalist it will go ahead?”*

Participant F: I would also go to a journalist in that case. Because you have a feeling that if you tell the journalist, it will go ahead.

Participant D: I think the media still has some power. Especially the traditional ones. In the past, if you threatened with the media when you got into a conflict, it helped. Now we don't have such problems or experiences anymore. But I would say that the media still have some power. If you are sure that you are right and that it is not going to continue, it is right to go to the media”.

Despite widespread criticism, citizens do not reject the media outright. On the contrary, they acknowledge several important strengths and democratic potentials—especially when it comes to public service media, the civic function of journalism, and the digital possibilities offered by social media.

Social platforms were appreciated for their speed, accessibility, and ability to engage younger audiences and foster participation—though always with the caveat that critical awareness is needed. Public broadcasters, though not without fault, were often seen as more balanced and reliable compared to commercial outlets and were valued for their commitment to neutrality and public interest.

Finally, media were recognised for their civic role when they support public debate, inform citizens, and amplify marginalised voices. In short, while trust in the media is cautious and conditional, citizens still believe in their democratic value—provided they evolve toward greater transparency, inclusion, and independence.

In summary

Negative Perceptions	
Lack of Impartiality	Media perceived as biased, politically influenced, and lacking objectivity.
Misinformation	Spread of fake news, contradictions, and unreliable sources—fueling distrust.
Economic & Political Pressure	Influence of owners, advertisers, and political actors seen as distorting content and priorities.
Low Content Quality	Sensationalism, superficial reporting, repetitive or trivial stories, especially on TV.
Journalistic Precarity	Poor working conditions lead to limited independence and professionalism.
Digital Media Risks	Social media associated with echo chambers, algorithms, polarization, and disinformation.
Censorship	Concerns about silenced journalists, lack of pluralism, and underrepresentation of minorities.
Negativity	Overfocus on negative news contributes to public anxiety and disengagement.

Positive Perceptions	
Civic Function	Media seen as tools for public debate, democratic awareness, and informed participation.
Social Media Potential	Valued for speed, accessibility, public expression, and engaging younger audiences.
Public Media Trust	Public broadcasters often perceived as more neutral, serious, and serving the public interest.
Democratic Hope	Citizens do not reject media—trust is cautious, but there's a clear desire for reform and improvement.

2.3 Expectations of the democratic role of the media

European citizens are not merely calling for *more* information—they are demanding *better* information: independent, pluralistic, accessible, and truly useful to democratic life.

1. Impartiality, Quality, and Transparency:

The strongest and most recurring demand is for greater impartiality and objectivity, followed closely by a desire for higher-quality journalism. Citizens express frustration with superficial reporting, sensationalism, and commercialised content. Instead, they call for deeper analysis, better programming, more constructive narratives, and a reduction in the excessive focus on negative news.

France: [FG.2] *“Being more neutral, does not try to make people hear what people expect. Don't try to say what people want to hear. Show more the reality”.*

Italy: [FG.2] *“If, on the other hand, a single message were sent to everyone, it would be easier. Everyone would receive the same neutral message and could make an informed choice”.*

Czech: [FG.1] *“Participant 6: I'd rather it be balanced. Not only negative things, not only positive, but something negative, something positive, because exactly, when it's only negative, people often think it's not worth it, nothing will change anyway, it's all crap here. And only positive, that's also bad. So just balance it”.*

2. Useful, Accessible, and Concrete Information

There is a clear expectation for political information to be accessible and easy to understand—well-structured, contextualised, and relevant to everyday life. Citizens want in-depth journalism, fact-checking, data-driven reporting, and more educational content. They also call for a journalism that connects with ordinary people, rather than focusing solely on elites, scandals, or polarised debate.

Czech: [FG.1] *“Participant 8: Especially consulting with people of all age groups. I like it when schools explain how elections work. I'd like to see more explanations of the impact of our politicians in the Chamber of Deputies and the European Parliament, like what influence they have. But in a simplified way, not through complex laws, just explaining it clearly—how it all works. I think that education is essential”.*

Slovenia: [FG.2] *Participant A: The best thing here, very generally, one actor said “Don't be the first one, be the right one.” When asked by the media for his opinion on the media. Don't compete to be the first to get the news out. Check it, study it, and get the truth out. And I agree with that 100%.*

3. Systemic Reform and Public Service Media:

Many participants call for a structural reform of the media system, stressing the need for greater independence—both editorial and financial. Public service media are seen as crucial actors, provided they remain politically neutral and accountable. Regulation is widely viewed as necessary to curb the

excesses of private and digital media. Citizens also suggest the creation of institutional information channels, more specialised reporting, and dedicated programming on referendums and civic matters.

Italy: [Int. 19] “A: One thing I would like to see in terms of communication is a public or European body that monitors television, at least the most important channels. This would ensure freedom of information; news must be reported, but it must all be verified. There should be no filtering or reworking of the truth. I don't know if this already exists, perhaps something called *Vigilanza Rai*, but I don't think that's enough. There should be something at European or international level to regulate information. In my opinion, there is a lot of work to be done on this issue, at the level of social media, Meta, agreements with states and between states, to guarantee freedoms. This is what I would like to see: information that is accessible to everyone, on all channels, true and objective, without fear of exposing oneself on objective matters, at least. This does not exist, and so I would like to see it”.

4. Participation, Pluralism, and Civic Responsibility:

Information is seen not just as a product, but as a tool for active citizenship. Participants want the media to encourage political participation, ensure pluralism of voices, create spaces for constructive debate, and pay greater attention to younger generations and local communities. The role of media in supporting democratic engagement is considered fundamental.

Poland: [FG. 1] ““Promotion of grassroots initiatives” is what we meant, for example, that there are all these incentives for the young: to the polls, women to the polls, and that it should also be presented more so in the media, let's say television, because some people don't use the Internet that much, but they will just find out that there is such a thing, well, and they can pick up the phone and type in Google and find out, for example, about this initiative”.

Slovenia: [FG. 1] “We should have more spectrums here, all covered. Right, left, here and there. Because that has a very strong influence on people's thinking and then on their decisions. And then also on democracy and development itself”.

2.4 Media Social Impact

Participants across Europe widely recognised the powerful influence media have on society, identifying them as key agents in shaping public opinion, mobilising participation, and affecting civic engagement. Media are not seen as neutral tools of information, but as active forces that can inspire, divide, inform, or manipulate—depending on how they are used and who controls them.

1. Media as Shapers of Opinion and Participation

The most mentioned impact of the media was their ability to shape opinions—a role acknowledged by a large majority of participants. Closely connected to this is the media’s influence on civic participation and public engagement. Citizens described the media as central to how people form their ideas, interpret political events, and decide whether or not to engage in democratic life.

Austria: [FG.1] *“I just sometimes ask myself whether the media can really bring about a representative democracy, because if I bring marketing into politics, as certain parties do, I don’t know whether people vote simply because marketing has worked or because they are really interested in it and have really dealt with it”.*

Czech: [FG.1] *“Participant 9: I, for example, during Covid, it personally influenced me at first, like, it kind of forced me, or like, people were pushed to get vaccinated a lot, but on the other hand, it kind of put some off, like it put me off at the start, because they were really scaring people with everything, how terrible everything was, and today Covid has pretty much passed. That definitely influenced me in that time. That I was really scared until it started to settle down”.*

2. Social Media: Double-Edged Tools of Influence

Social media emerged as powerful yet ambivalent platforms. Participants recognised their speed, reach, and accessibility, especially among young people, who rely heavily on them for information and political content. However, there was widespread concern about algorithm-driven echo chambers, polarisation, and the risk of superficial or biased exposure to information. Social media were seen as shaping voting behaviour, reinforcing existing opinions, and potentially undermining democratic dialogue by limiting access to diverse perspectives. While some valued their participatory potential, many viewed them as a threat to critical thinking and pluralism—especially for less informed or younger users.

Germany: [FG.2] *“if you’ve just been allowed to vote for the first time, at 16, 18 or so, then you might be on TikTok or Instagram a lot or whatever. Or maybe some are still on Twitter or X. And I think that has a big influence on voting decisions, because the algorithm amplifies a lot of things and I think that you can be influenced very easily, especially at a young age”.*

Portugal: [FG.1] *“The way the model is set up increases the polarisation of opinions. Because I have certain interests, I think in a certain way, certain tastes, the algorithm will bring me more of that and, therefore, I think this is a disservice to democracy, because democracy is about accepting all differences and listening. But these algorithms are polarising”.*

Media Expectations and Social Impact		
Dimension	Positive Expectations & Functions	Concerns & Risks
Impartiality & Quality	Desire for neutral, balanced, well-researched journalism with constructive and informative narratives.	Frustration with sensationalism, superficial coverage, and media bias (political/economic).
Accessibility & Usefulness	Call for clear, contextualised, fact-based news that connects with everyday life and helps citizens make informed choices.	News often too complex, elite-focused, or disconnected from ordinary people's lives.
Systemic Reform & Regulation	Support for independent public service media, stronger media regulation, and pan-European oversight bodies.	Concerns about commercial influence, lack of editorial independence, and weak regulation of digital media.
Participation & Pluralism	Media should promote democratic engagement, reflect diverse views, and encourage youth and community involvement.	Fear of exclusion, echo chambers, and underrepresentation of grassroots and minority voices.
Media's Influence on Opinion & Civic Life	Media seen as powerful drivers of public opinion, democratic awareness, and civic mobilisation.	Risk of manipulation, over-reliance on marketing, and emotional influence (e.g. fear-driven coverage).
Role of Social Media	Valued for accessibility, speed, and participatory potential—especially for youth.	Risks of algorithm-driven echo chambers, misinformation, polarisation, and reduced critical thinking.

2.5 Media Trust & Distrust

The data reveal a nuanced and layered picture of how European citizens relate to different media sources. Trust in the media is not binary—it is neither absolute nor entirely absent—but rather selective, conditional, and shaped by perceived values such as impartiality, professionalism, and independence.

- 1) **Traditional media** still hold a central position in public trust. Despite the ongoing digital transformation, traditional outlets retain credibility, especially when associated with in-depth

reporting and editorial quality. Print media and local papers, however, appear far less influential, suggesting a declining trust or relevance in more fragmented, localized journalism.

Ireland: [FG.2] *“Speaker F7: I still believe what I hear on the 6o’clock news. I still believe what I hear on the 6o’clock news. I watch it every night. I do”.*

Italy: [FG.1] *“(M, 23): If a politician speaks on TV, I trust them more than social media”.*

Portugal: [FG.3] *“I would probably place the written press first, as it has more investigative journalism, Expresso and Público, and RTP2 and RTP1. But I believe it's important not to focus only on one”.*

2. **Public media**, in particular, are strongly associated with positive attributes. They are seen as potentially more neutral, balanced, and reliable, especially when compared to private outlets, which were mentioned much less frequently. This indicates a public hope—or perhaps expectation—that public broadcasters can act as guardians of democratic values, provided they remain free from political or commercial pressures.

Czech: [FG.1] *“Participant 10: I have a lot of trust in public television because it's set up in a way that it's not supposed to be influenced. So, I think many people trust it”.*

France: [Int.10] *“Afterwards, I still have, I think, confidence in public broadcasting, whether it be France Info, France Télévision. I find that they still manage more or less to talk a little about everything, to invite everyone and also to do good surveys”.*

3. **The role of journalists** emerges as pivotal in shaping public trust. References to professionalism, independence and impartiality suggest that trust in the media is often a proxy for trust in the individuals who produce and deliver information. Citizens seem to value ethical and competent journalism, capable of resisting external influence and avoiding sensationalism. The journalist, in this sense, becomes not just a messenger but a symbol of accountability.

France: [Int.4] *“DP: There are independent media, there are small media, even clandestine but these disclosures, they do it. For example, El Café picante, in the conversation, and in the joke, I don't know if you knew Jaime Garzon within his videos”.*

Italy: [Int.10] *“I trust a YouTube channel much more, sometimes, which is self-financed with its own production, which is self-financed, which perhaps asks its subscribers for money, with a subscription, therefore self-financed, compared to a television channel. Where Rai has political management, Canale 5 historically has a right-wing slant and, in short, Rai Tre is communist television, in inverted commas. There, you know what to expect. But if I want to find more neutral information, I look elsewhere”.*

At the same time, while social media are mentioned less frequently in relation to trust, they still reveal recurring patterns and meaningful nuances. Among these, YouTube stands out as a platform perceived

to offer relatively more trustworthy content. Its accessibility, combined with the possibility for users to engage in open discussion, contributes to a sense of credibility.

Czech: [FG.1] *“On social media, I trust specific YouTubers who I know do thorough research when creating their informative videos”.*

Italy: [Int.25] *“A: I don't know who owns the newspapers on social media, so I avoid them because there are right-wing and left-wing newspapers and, obviously, the article and the author's opinion will lean towards one side or the other. So, not knowing, I avoid them. On YouTube, on the other hand, I listened to several people and in the end I narrowed it down to these two for now because they seem more objective to me. It's too important for me to form an opinion that isn't influenced”.*

Rather than trusting the system as a whole, citizens seem to navigate the media environment carefully, often resorting to critical consumption and personal judgment to assess reliability.

Austria: [FG.4] *“I think everything you read on the internet [should] be taken with a pinch of salt”.*

Czech: [FG.1] *Participant 9: I don't have a specific source where I get all my information. I read a bit of everything that seems sensible to me and then form my own opinion.*

Poland: [FG.2] *“if you want to check some information, to be sure, you have to look for it yourself in many, many sources”.*

Distrust, instead, is not limited to particular platforms or practices but often reflects a deeper, structural disillusionment. This suggests that many citizens no longer see the media as neutral or reliable intermediaries of information, but rather as actors whose agendas, methods, and content are often questioned or distrusted by default. Such skepticism reflects a crisis of confidence in the informational system as a whole—one that may be rooted in past misinformation, perceived manipulation, or fatigue from conflicting narratives.

Czech: [FG.1] *“Sometimes when I look at Seznam, then Novinky or another site, the articles seem identical, just with different headlines. Also, sometimes the sentence structure doesn't make sense, and I think, “Who knows who wrote this?” It seems like it was quickly typed out without much thought, and I don't trust the information when it's presented like that”.*

Portugal: [FG.3] *“Now, the news is painted in a very dark light, making us feel afraid to leave the house. And this is also due to the global politics that lead to the misrepresentation of all the news that exists. Trusting the media? I don't trust the media. Is there a better system? Perhaps not selling the news and instead delivering it in a truthful way”.*

1. Social Media: Visibility Without Credibility

Social media platforms are frequently cited in relation to distrust revealing that high exposure does not equate to high credibility. These platforms are commonly associated with Partisanship, Echo chambers and Sensationalism.

France: [FG.2] *“The problem is that you can be completely anonymous. You can post something, but post with a fake account. It's dangerous, suddenly. Yes, social networks, in fact, are very dangerous for that. There is a lot of fake news”.*

Italy: [Int.5] *“I don't usually take news on social media as true, so I start from that assumption, and then for the others I look for other sources to see if they are fake or not. But let's say that the news I read on social media, when I scroll through it, I almost never take it as true”.*

Although social media are praised elsewhere for accessibility and participatory potential—especially among younger generations—these data show that they are equally viewed as fertile ground for misinformation, manipulation, and ideological polarization.

Slovenia: [FG.1] *“There are a lot of untruths, there is a lot of fake news. And unfortunately it's the case that everybody is aware, but nobody has the time to check. You see something. If it's too sensational, you know it's not true”.*

2. Traditional Media and Television: Not Immune to Critique

While less central to expressions of distrust, traditional media—especially television—are not spared from criticism. Television is mentioned in this context, with private broadcasters more frequently associated with negative perceptions. This shows that while traditional media may benefit from institutional credibility, they are not exempt from citizen concerns about objectivity, quality, and intent.

France: [FG.3] *“I have less confidence in television media than in a journal. The journalist is involved. He wrote an article. This is rarely useful except in television media”.*

Estonia: [Int.M] *“I think, with the scale of trust I've come to believe in, I would put social media first. It's more immediate access to a broader kind of followership. But it does feel a little bit more real than to read a newspaper or watch a TV broadcast, or listen to the radio”.*

Across all forms, the media face a growing and widespread crisis of trust. Citizens no longer question just individual platforms—they question the integrity of the system as a whole. Social media are seen as accessible but unreliable, often associated with misinformation, manipulation, and ideological bias. Traditional media, while still carrying institutional weight, are also viewed critically, especially for perceived partisanship and declining editorial standards.

2.6 Media Habits

The analysis reveals a growing awareness among European citizens about the need to adopt a critical, diversified, and active approach to the media. Many users recognize that the best way to stay informed accurately is not to rely on a single source, but to compare multiple different sources, exploring various perspectives.

Czech: [FG.3] *“Participant 22: Everyone must have their own opinion, not just consume it”.*

France: [FG.1] “on social networks, I try to look at all the points of view, even if I really don't agree with them at all. And that allows me to try to understand what everyone thinks and what everyone can think”.

Italy: [FG.4] “P2 (F, 53): I take a little bit here and there, because I'm a bit distrustful. I always question things a little”.

Poland: [FG.2] “Don't believe. Check”.

This attitude of comparison and independent verification reflects a willingness to move beyond passive consumption of news and take on a more active and responsible role in the information process. This awareness is a positive sign, indicating that, faced with the complexity of today's media ecosystem, more and more people understand the importance of developing critical skills and independent research abilities to navigate the flow of available information with greater confidence.

In Summary

Media Habits, Trust & Distrust	
Trust in Media	Trust is selective and conditional, based on perceived impartiality, professionalism, and independence.
Traditional Media	Still central—especially public TV and quality print media—seen as more reliable than social media.
Public Broadcasters	Viewed as potential guardians of democracy, if free from political and commercial influence.
Role of Journalists	Trust often placed in individual journalists rather than platforms; valued for ethics, expertise, and independence.
Social Media	High visibility, low credibility—linked to fake news, echo chambers, anonymity, and manipulation.
Systemic Distrust	A broader crisis of confidence in the entire media ecosystem, not just in specific platforms.
Media Habits	Growing awareness of the need to compare sources, verify facts, and think critically.
Active Engagement	Citizens increasingly adopt a pluralistic and responsible approach to consuming information.

POLITICAL PARTICIPATION

3.1 Activities

European citizens possess a broad and nuanced understanding of political participation within democratic systems. Their perspective transcends traditional electoral practices, embracing a wide range of formal and informal activities, both individual and collective, that contribute to democratic life.

1) Institutional participation

At the core of democratic engagement lies institutional participation—those formal mechanisms designed to channel citizens' voices into governance processes. Voting remains the most universally recognized act of political participation, often regarded as the fundamental right and duty of citizenship.

Czech: [FG.1] *“Participant 6: Voting, in my opinion. Voting is the foundation. Participant 1: I also think it's the fundamental cornerstone, just going to vote”*

However, while voting is seen as essential, many citizens express mixed feelings about its actual impact on political outcomes. Beyond elections, instruments such as referendums and direct contact with elected officials are also valued for their potential to foster more direct influence and accountability within political systems.

Italy: [Int.23] *“Citizens could make their voices heard by proposing referendums. I very much welcome the fact that referendums can also be signed online”.*

Portugal: [Int.10] *“The first basic thing is to vote, okay? It's voting and interacting, for example, interacting with political figures, I don't know. Seeking information about the parties, what the parties stand for, and if necessary, running for office, joining a party, running for office. I think it's all of that, but the main foundation of democracy is that people have the freedom to vote”.*

2) Active participation

Active participation is recognised not only in institutional contexts, but also through grassroots practices such as protests, petitions and civic committees. These forms of direct involvement are concrete tools through which citizens seek to influence decision-making processes, express their dissent or support collective causes. **Demonstrations and strikes** are perceived as moments of visible and shared citizenship, although there is a certain disillusionment about their effectiveness, often linked to the risk of violence or a sense of powerlessness in the face of political inaction.

Italy: [FG.2] *“P5 (M, 28): Demonstrations, strikes. Moments when people take action, not only for their own interests but perhaps also for other groups. Perhaps taxi drivers are demonstrating, and even though I'm not a taxi driver, I support their cause and demonstrate with them, or with students or doctors”.*

Czech: [FG.1] *“Participant 7: I think protests don't have much weight anymore. Thanks to Babiš, who mocked the largest protest, they haven't had the same impact since then”.*

Italy: [Int.11] *“Doing it like a riot is useless. There's no need for riots. I think we need more dialogue, the ability to listen and talk. Even an idea that could be positive, if it comes across as a mob or shows no respect for the police, I don't like it. Instead, it would be nice to be able to express our opinions together in the square, with knowledge and respect”.*

At the same time, tools such as **petitions and local committees** offer more peaceful and accessible spaces for expression, through which citizens seek to be heard, gain visibility and collaborate, rediscovering the power of collective participation even in everyday, non-conflictual contexts.

France: [Int.11] *“I happened to sign a petition on the subjects I mentioned to you. I did that. With, how to say, not necessarily any illusion about the impact, but to need to have found somewhere a piece of space where I could express myself, directly, even if it is not taken into account behind. There are two or three key topics that we've raised. I've done that”.*

Germany: [FG.1] *“P8: I would add that the topic of elections and demonstrations definitely also includes petitions, or simply networking, founding associations, organizations (ahem)... Yes, I think that's also super important because there's this powerlessness. Because you feel so alone, as the only person, you don't manage to achieve anything. You tend to focus on: Okay, what can I do here and now? Where can I find like-minded people who also care about a certain issue? And that way you realize, okay, you can achieve more in a group, it's more effective”.*

3) Civic and Social Participation

The data collected show that civic and social participation is a fundamental component of the democratic experience. Activities such as volunteering, community life and associationism are perceived as concrete expressions of a “bottom-up” democracy, capable of strengthening social ties and promoting cohesion.

Austria: [FG.1] *“P2: There are many ways to get involved. Most people aren't interested in them. There are lots of associations, whether they are politically orientated or not. And there are lots of neighbourhood associations, neighbourhood clubs, NGOs. I'm involved in a children's hospice and so on and so forth. You can do a lot of voluntary work”.*

Estonia: Person A: *Who can and wants to, all kinds of opinion festivals, all kinds of community centres and things like that, which are on a smaller level. Those are places where you can have your say if you have the energy. And in fact, it's much easier to make a difference in a tiny village community somewhere than it is at the national or larger city level. If you've got four or five able people in a tiny village somewhere who get together and put their heads and their skills*

Alongside these more visible forms, equally significant practices are emerging, such as everyday solidarity, social responsibility, education and the dissemination of knowledge, which, although less structured, embody deeply democratic values and contribute to building a sense of belonging and collective commitment.

Germany: [FG.4] P7: *Well, that you educate yourself regularly, that you read different things, that you form an opinion, that you have an exchange, that you discuss it, that you have a certain*

idea of the current topics and then form an opinion. Whether it's one way or the other, it doesn't matter, does it? I think that's very important.

4) Discursive and informal participation

Engagement in democracy also thrives through informal, everyday actions that center on dialogue and critical reflection. Active information-seeking, cultural exchanges, and participation in public debates are vital for nurturing an informed electorate and sustaining democratic pluralism. Citizens recognize the importance of discussing current affairs, exchanging diverse viewpoints, and cultivating a public sphere where democracy can be practiced not only through formal acts but also through ongoing social interaction.

France: [FG.2] *“PE (M, 19): Above all, it would be active information that should be obtained. It would be necessary to learn a lot about the subject, take time, truly create a constructive opinion and not just brief ideas”.*

Austria: [FG.1] *“P9: Yes, I think exchanging ideas, although I have the feeling that this has somehow become old-fashioned. So, taking part in discussions, going to information events. Yes, maybe also (...) reading and researching a lot. Yes, in that direction...”*

Czech: [FG.3] *“Participant 22: Democracy isn't just about politics, but also about people coming together and talking”.*

5) Alternative and symbolic forms

Alongside traditional and active participation, citizens also engage in symbolic or alternative acts that express political attitudes in non-conventional ways. Choosing not to vote or selectively engaging with information can be deliberate acts of dissent, signalling dissatisfaction with the status quo. Such practices reflect a desire to maintain agency and critical distance in a complex political environment, underscoring that participation takes many forms beyond direct action.

Italy: P4 (m, 61): *Not voting is also a vote. Statistically, I am at least in the group that has not been voting for a few years. There was a time when the Five Star Movement appealed to me a little, but then they too fell into the trap of democracy in power, like everyone else. For ten years, it was the Left with the Centre, and now it's the Right, but the same old problems remain.*

Similarly, actions such as contacting the media, fact-checking or, conversely, avoiding certain information channels express critical and selective participation, reflecting a desire not to passively accept information but to consciously navigate the media landscape, reaffirming one's active role in public discourse.

Czech: [FG.1] *“Participant 1: Maybe debunking populist opinions on social media or elsewhere.*

Participant 2: But how?

Participant 1: On social media, for example, or in a village pub. That makes me think of maybe explaining to seniors how things are today because I feel like they are stuck in the old regime, and there are still some parties from before. So, they don't have access to social media, and they often vote for the parties they know. Maybe explain what the possibilities are and help them navigate it.

Participant 10: Not supporting extremist parties or extremists in politics in general.

Moderator: And how would you do that? Through voting, for example?

Participant 10: Voting, or even by not spreading it on social media”.

This multifaceted understanding of political participation highlights the richness of democratic involvement across Europe. Citizens employ a variety of strategies and channels to engage, challenge, and shape their political realities, emphasizing that democracy flourishes not only through elections but through everyday acts of civic commitment and collective dialogue.

3.2 Barriers to participation

Although political participation is widely recognised as an essential element of democracy, data highlights a number of obstacles that severely limit its effective realisation. The responses collected show that many citizens face a widespread sense of mistrust, disillusionment and distance from the political system, accompanied by personal, cultural, social and economic barriers. These difficulties not only reduce the effectiveness of individual participation but also contribute to reinforcing dynamics of exclusion and disengagement.

1. Distrust in politics

A fundamental and widespread barrier to participation is deep scepticism towards politics and political actors. Many citizens feel ignored and powerless, perceiving political institutions as ineffective, corrupt, or disconnected from everyday concerns. This lack of trust erodes motivation to engage and fosters disengagement.

Slovenia: [FG.4] *“Participant 1: Our street is covered with pigeons. I think I wrote 2 e-mails to the inspectorate. I wrote 2 e-mails to the mayor, we were on TV ... Our street is still covered with pigeons and nobody moves anything. What am I supposed to do about it?”*

Politics is perceived as ineffective or corrupted, with broken promises, lack of representation, and distance between citizens and institutions, both national and European.

Italy: [FG.2] *“I hear many people saying the same thing: ‘It's always the same, they all do the same thing. Yes, there is a political difference, but regardless of who you vote for, the political situation is always the same, so I don't vote.’ I have heard several people say this to me, and I saw this with the European elections, with a disastrous turnout. And I am led to believe that many people find themselves in this situation and therefore do not vote”.*

Portugal: [FG.2] *“I think that's what people often don't believe in at the moment, and I often say that people who are good and want to do well don't go into politics. Because I feel that sometimes people get there with good intentions, but they get there and they become discouraged. And it's a bit corrupt. And I think that people are probably not that bothered either and it's hard enough to organise a Friday dinner, let alone a whole party. I think that people nowadays probably don't have as much resilience either and I think it's a very specific profile that ends up following politics. And that's why it all seems the same to us today”.*

2. Distrust in personal power and role

Beyond mistrust in political systems, many individuals doubt their own ability to influence political outcomes. A common feeling is that individual actions or complaints are insignificant, fueling frustration and apathy. This sense of futility often stems from limited recognition or lack of practical tools to engage effectively.

Austria: [FG.2] *“ I think there is a kind of fake participation and that is something that creates frustration. I'm allowed to have a say, but I have absolutely no influence on decisions. So when (...) people say: It doesn't really matter who's at the helm anyway”.*

Czech: [FG.1] *“why I don't vote, I feel like it might get lost in the masses. So, it's not really worth the time invested”.*

3. Criticism of the role of the media

Media, a key channel for political information and participation, are often perceived as obstacles rather than enablers. Citizens complain about a lack of relevant, accessible, and timely political coverage, especially concerning grassroots activities or youth engagement. Media content is frequently seen as biased, sensationalist, or discouraging, which diminishes trust and interest.

Italy: P8(F, 24): *If there were already news on TV, in newspapers, or on the radio saying, ‘Today there will be stands...’, and in any case newspapers are read by many people, as are TV and radio, the public would be more informed about these things.*

Slovenia: [FG.1] *“we don't get enough information. Let's say, tomorrow I will only find out that something happened yesterday that I'd be interested in”.*

France: [Int. 11] *“I also think that it can directly generate frustration to always hear an orientation. So, either I will listen to the media that always goes in my direction. If I found one, well, finally, it's comfortable. But I think it can be... In any case, I hear a lot of people around me frustrated because of that too. I continue to go from one media to another. I listened to France Inter throughout my youth. At home, it was France Inter. I've listened to France Inter all my life, in fact. And I'm tired of always hearing it slanted in the same direction. Precisely because it's public, I'd like this radio to bring about a debate. And I enjoy it and I still listen to a lot of shows. The humor is always oriented in the same direction, etc. And I think that's a shame. We have lost in this public media space”.*

4. Cultural and educational barriers

A significant obstacle is the lack of political knowledge and civic education, which leaves many confused about how to participate or the importance of doing so. Without clear understanding or guidance, citizens may withdraw from political engagement, perpetuating a cycle of ignorance and abstention.

Italy: *Many, for lots of reasons, including political ignorance, can't make decisions and prefer to abstain, which I think is wrong. Precisely because it's a power given to us, I think we should use it to the full. It's not fair that so many people don't take advantage of it; it's a right they're denying themselves, but it's a very special right, for us, for all Italian citizens. We have worked so hard to get it... it is a waste.*

Portugal: [FG.1] “Lack of training, lack of education. We had to have more educators and more trainers at all levels”.

Austria: [FG.3] “P7: I find [it's] very difficult to get correct and good information. And this party programme, you also have to..., you first have to [find it and then understand] what they really want and the way there is too long for me. [If] you know straight away: OK, this party does this, I know my way around, this is what I want, then I might be more likely to vote, because then I know what I want, or... But these are usually posters that say something on , something that doesn't work”.

5. Emotional and social barriers

Emotions such as fear, shame, and anxiety also act as significant deterrents to political participation. In polarized or hostile environments, individuals may fear retaliation, social exclusion, or personal harm, especially minorities or dissenting voices.

France: [Int. 10] “PJ: Hate speeches, speeches by Jean-Marie Le Pen, by Éric Zemmour, by his girlfriend, people like that, people who in municipalities burn cars, where mayors from the Front National and who say that it's the Arabs. This kind of thing, that's the danger for me. And when you see them all the time and they talk, then there are consequences”.

Poland: [FG.1] “I think to myself that in Poland very often taking part in some actions that are associated with politics is considered a shame. And I think about the fact that if we know someone who has participated in such actions, then maybe we become more accustomed to it, that there is nothing wrong with going to a political demonstration and that normal people also take part in it, and not just, I don't know, some paid agents”.

Austria: [FG.3] “P2: I don't know. You're afraid of doing something wrong. So now I've been to the elections or the democratic right...I have a child, I don't want to go demonstrating with my daughter for other things. I don't know what to vote for. There are, I don't know, five left-wing

parties and one right-wing party. Yes, you're afraid of doing the wrong thing, of voting for the wrong thing”.

The risk of exposing oneself publicly or being judged limits political expression, especially for minorities or opposition groups.

Italy: [Int.30] *“For me, quite simply, it's much harder to walk in a march, and if violence breaks out, I'm the first to end up on the ground. They scare me a lot. Once, they really scared me. They were extremely dangerous situations from my point of view. Even the noise... it's not for me. Maybe that's why I don't participate much, besides the fact that maybe I do participate and then at some point they put out a new message that I don't agree with”.*

6. Practical and logistical obstacles

Finally, concrete practical barriers also restrict participation, disproportionately affecting marginalized groups. These include difficulties in voting procedures, lack of time, bureaucratic hurdles, and geographic distance from polling stations or political events. The digital divide and inaccessible information further exacerbate exclusion.

Czech: [FG.4] *“Participant 38: I think it generally discourages people from voting because, for example, if you start taking an interest in politics at 35 or, for instance, my parents, who are around 50 and never really went to vote much, my brother and I managed to convince them that it's important, not just for them but also for us. It took long evenings of watching, reading, explaining, and communicating, but not everyone can handle that or wants to spend that much time and effort thinking about it. It's easier to just not go to vote and say it doesn't matter because it doesn't matter who you vote for”.*

Estonia: [Int.A] *“Person A: It's maybe not the most important thing, but in a way it's very important. What a friend of mine once said to me is that a lot of parties and politicians and others, they actually talk over the head of the average person. Which is also absolutely, some of the Social Democrats agree with that. The things that they are planning and want to do and all of their principles are talked about in such a way that you have to be in the know or at least you have to be in a way political or at least have a higher education to understand these things. It goes over the head of the average Estonian”.*

The digital divide, accessibility of information and lack of transparency are also concrete factors that discourage engagement.

Italy: [FG.2] *“In my opinion, there is a gap between people who live very well and the middle class that has lost out. I don't know, people who can't afford a smartphone have to worry so much about keeping their jobs that they can't even think about protesting or going on strike. Because if I go on strike now and the company fires me, I have a family to support, including my wife and two children, and maybe my wife doesn't work, so I can't support my family. So there's also the issue of not being able to afford to protest or complain. There's general discontent, you lose faith in your government and you don't want to vote anymore, and you try to survive as best you can. That's also something to consider”.*

Although citizens recognise the vital importance of political participation, it is clearly undermined by profound mistrust in institutions and the media, a fragile sense of individual efficacy, cultural and emotional hurdles, and practical challenges. There is a widespread demand for greater transparency, genuine dialogue, inclusiveness, and tangible tools that empower people to make a real difference. Without addressing these barriers, many find no viable space in which to engage meaningfully in democratic life.

3.3 Encouragements to participation

Despite widespread obstacles to political participation, many citizens clearly express a desire to be more actively and meaningfully involved in democratic life. The testimonies gathered highlight a strong demand for conditions that make participation not only possible, but also effective and motivating. Among the proposals that emerged, the need for more credible and accessible politics, transparent and participatory media, widespread civic education, and simpler and more inclusive ways of participating were highlighted. At the heart of it all is the demand for recognition, listening and real impact: only when these conditions are met will citizens feel encouraged to take action again and contribute first-hand to the construction of democracy.

1. More credible, accessible and transparent politics

Citizens call for clearer communication, more consistency between promises and actions, and greater openness from political actors. There's a strong desire for spaces where dialogue is possible, such as local debates and public meetings, and for new political figures who are perceived as closer and more representative.

Austria: [FG.2] “P4: Simply give people more opportunities (um) to get involved in this discussion process. So more, more discussions at community level, where people are simply invited to join in and have their say. And that doesn't have to be limited [only] to this area. Simply make this offer from the administration, from the parties, make this offer globally (...)... It's not a party event, it's just four different parties sitting there and making this offer: Come and talk to us, tell us your concerns”.

Italy: A: At the local level, they should organise more political meetings and debates in cities. I really like them and see them a lot on TV. I've never been to one in person, but it would be nice. And it's definitely something that young people are passionate about, even though politics has no age limit. In my opinion, it's a solution that would work well. Organising political festivals, where politicians present their ideas, there's a debate, a moderator. It's something I'd like and it would also work well for other target audiences. So not just on TV, but also live.

France: [FG.4] “PI (M, 42): Sometimes we talk about simplification, we talk about accessibility. It has to be simple. Because in fact, I have the impression that they come out of the cobblestones on purpose. Do you want information? No worries. Hey, there are 70 binders. A simple thing should exist!”

2. More accessible, clear and participatory media

Media—both traditional and digital—play a crucial role in shaping civic engagement. Citizens call for more accessible, neutral, and informative content that explains political choices clearly, promotes respectful debate, and highlights civic initiatives. There's a strong preference for formats that are simple, short, and appealing—especially for younger audiences. Campaigns that connect emotionally or humorously, and avoid polarisation, are more likely to encourage attention and participation.

Czech: *humanizing politics because for many people, it's complicated, and they don't want to deal with it. I get that when you watch a debate like on Václav Moravec's show, where two people are yelling at each other, it's hard for the moderator to control them, and no one really enjoys it. Maybe also more campaigns like "Convince Grandma" or something similar that resonates with society and reminds people that elections are happening and why they should vote. But in a non-violent, entertaining way.*

Germany: *P1: Maybe simplify the content in general, because many young people are on reels or shorts or something like that, for example. Is it possible to somehow reel off party platforms within 30 seconds? So that you can perhaps get some information.*

Estonia: *Participant H: I would say that it might help to overcome the fears if there were channels that presented different ideas; channels that wouldn't present it like 'I think this way and this is pure gold and if you think differently then you're dumb and mistaken', but in a more neutral way. And when you don't really understand why we are even discussing this topic, then it is summarised for you in a simple way which you can grasp more easily.*

3. Civic and Political Education

Across the board, there is consensus on the need to invest in civic education—not only in schools, but throughout life. This includes learning how institutions function, understanding political ideologies, practising respectful debate, and recognising one's rights and responsibilities. Education is seen as key to breaking the cycle of disinterest and disillusionment, especially among young people, who are often underrepresented and less engaged. Citizens ask not just to be informed, but to be empowered.

Austria: *[FG.1] "P4: I would somehow suggest an old-school method of simply increasing the presence in real life again - with meetings in different cities. So, not just talks [on] Puls 4 or in a pub, where most people of a certain age group come anyway, but you should make more school visits to educational centres and also attend university discussions as politicians".*

Italy: *[FG.2] "We need to raise awareness. What does voting for Meloni mean? What does her party stand for? That would also be a way for people to understand their own political orientation. Because if I don't know who to vote for because I don't know which parties reflect my ideas, then I lose interest and the will to vote. For me, therefore, it's a vicious circle that sets in, and people who want to vote don't have the physical means to do so. And that's how we end up in the current situation".*

Slovenia: [FG.3] *“Participant C: I think young people should be more involved in elections. Because, as I said before, when I'm involved in electoral commissions, we need to keep statistics by age. And young people are maybe 20%, but more than 50% are over 65. So I would say that the younger generations are very poor voters. I think that young people should be encouraged to participate and should be told that nothing is going to change without them taking part in elections. Nothing.*

Participant A: It seems to me that young people are being made sufficiently aware of the importance of elections. It's just that they still don't believe the stories enough to find it worthwhile.

Participant B: I would add here that they are not taught enough about it”.

4. Reforming Participation Tools

People are asking for more ways—and better ways—to engage. Proposals include simplifying voting procedures, strengthening direct democracy tools like referendums, experimenting with new formats such as citizens' assemblies, and rethinking electoral systems to make political choices more meaningful. Some suggest mandatory voting, others propose age limits for candidates. But overall, the request is the same: make democratic tools functional, inclusive, and responsive.

In this context, **many look to France as a model**—not of perfection, but of active civic resistance. French citizens are often admired for their willingness to mobilise collectively when faced with injustice or unpopular policies. This is seen as a sign of a healthy, assertive democratic culture—where protest, visibility, and collective action are used to defend rights and shape outcomes. The contrast with more passive or resigned attitudes elsewhere is striking and often serves as a wake-up call.

Italy: [FG.3] *“We are not capable of doing what the French did, with clashes and revolutions, as the French example teaches us. Instead of voting, let's organise a big demonstration and start rounding up those who have been causing trouble. Unfortunately, it is obvious that some violence may break out, because we are not all the same, but if there were a big demonstration in the streets...”*

Portugal: [FG.4] *“I'll give an extreme example from France, where they always work. It's very extreme, the protests in France. But here in Portugal, we see people going and striking, then the machinists strike. In France, everyone goes on strike. There's a common cause. And if the nurses aren't doing well, the whole country stops until the nurses are heard. I think that in Portugal, we don't have that sense of general unity like the French”.*

Estonia: [Int.J] *“I think France is a very good example of a democratic society, because whenever something goes against, you know, their way, they just protest. They're not afraid to kind of stop the city, you know, even when it comes at a cost. You know, it's disruptive and it's not pretty, but at least, you know, you can see the will of the people. They're not afraid to voice their opinions and to make a change. They're not like blind puppets. I really admire that. I think that's the core of any democratic society. I think they are a very good example of what it needs to be. So that's kind of my opinion”.*

5. Relationships, proximity and tangible results are key to reactivating participation.

A recurring theme is the power of local communities and close social ties. Participation feels easier and more rewarding when it is rooted in trust, solidarity, and shared goals. Proximity matters—whether geographical, relational, or cultural. Citizens are more inclined to act when they see their efforts contribute to something tangible and when mutual respect and collaboration are present. Volunteering, neighbourhood initiatives, and symbolic actions often serve as stepping stones into broader civic life.

Austria: [FG.1] *“the example of “voluntary”:* well, there is a huge difference between us in Vienna and the federal state or the provinces. There are actually 1.3 million people doing voluntary work. Me too, but in many different areas. The point is that it's lived there [in the country] and in Vienna it's completely different. You don't even know your neighbour, one floor above you. And that's one of the things that makes it difficult to get involved in voluntary work. Because that's how volunteering works: Don't you fancy popping round? Have a look at it... It's difficult in the city, but it works perfectly in the countryside”.

Estonia: [FG.3] *“Participant D: Just like Participant A, I live... I don't live in Tallinn; I live in a small town near Tallinn already for 20 years. And there, I can influence things with my own activities in order to feel good there. There, it's really the case that if something good or bad is done, then... well, if something is off, then the municipal mayor is notified and reacts immediately; things start happening basically in an instant, rather than in half a year or whatever. The mayor is very active and really wants and tries to make it so that it wouldn't be a bedroom suburb, and so forth. But yes—all change is hard, right? When people want to improve something, the evergreen response is ‘Let's do it how we've always done it’, he-he. But since I can influence things myself, right, and see that my children are growing up in a good environment... I think in Tallinn, it is much more anonymous—it gets... your word gets lost here. But the further you go from Tallinn, the more you can do to influence it yourself...”*

Finally, participation must be seen to work. Many express frustration at efforts that seem to go nowhere—blocked by bureaucracy or ignored by decision-makers. Motivation depends on outcomes. When people experience “small victories” or even symbolic recognition, they feel more inclined to engage again. What citizens ultimately seek is not perfection, but a sense that their voice matters, that something changes because of it.

Slovenia: [FG.2] *“Participant D: I think there should be some small victories for the people. That maybe more people would try to make some change. Because I agree with that. You, let's say, as an individual or as a group, are trying and trying to do something. But in the end you will not do anything because somewhere some bigot will call somebody and say that it will not go through. And all your efforts, or the efforts of several people, are in vain and for nothing”.*

In summary, people want to participate—but they need fertile ground to do so. This means credible and responsive politics, transparent and inclusive media, strong civic education, and effective tools for engagement. Political participation does not grow in a vacuum; it is nourished by trust, proximity,

knowledge, and recognition. When these elements are in place, participation becomes not only possible—but natural.

PARTECIPATION THROUGH THE MEDIA

Citizens recognise that both digital and traditional media can be useful tools for participating in democratic life. However, the opinions gathered show strong ambivalence: the opportunities offered, especially by social media, to obtain information, express opinions and mobilise quickly are appreciated; on the other hand, there is a lot of criticism regarding the quality of the debate, the spread of hate and disinformation, and the perception of limited impact. The following analysis brings together the main perceptions that emerged, highlighting both the positive aspects and the difficulties that hinder effective participation through the media.

4.1 Positive aspects

1. **Social media** are the most frequently mentioned tools for political participation, especially among young people. They are valued for their potential to:

- Share opinions and content
- Sign online petitions or campaigns
- Get information and mobilise quickly
- Community fact-checking

Czech: [FG.4] “Participant 30: I really like the community corrections on Twitter, where there's some information, and below it, there's the real story. I think that's great. I understand that something similar is harder to do on TV, but I think it would be great if it existed. Some context for the information, maybe”.

Estonia: [FG.1] “Participant D: Social media is today open to everyone, and there you can... you can become an influencer [?] and then you're the one who... the one who can impose his opinion”.

2. For citizens less familiar with digital tools, **traditional media**—such as television, radio, and newspapers—still play a relevant role in enabling visibility and triggering political responses.

France: [FG.3] “PE (M, 50): Yes, to call on a journalist during a factory closure, for example, that they intervene with photographers, cameras, everything necessary to make politicians react, precisely. So that's a way to do it.

M: Have you ever asked for a newspaper?

PE (M, 50): Yes. In my professional case, when I opened an agency, I asked the local newspaper to come and write an article”.

3. **Digital participatory tools:** Some participants refer to newer tools that support direct expression and visibility, such as:

- Online platforms
- Digital petitions, surveys,
- Apps, blogs: alternative tools for expressing opinions and staying informed.

Czech: [FG.4] *“Participant 30: Seznam has a platform called Seznam Médium, where people can write their articles, and if they’re good, they get some publicity among those who follow it. So that’s one way to publicly express your views.*

Moderator: Like writing an article.

Participant 30: Yes, or a comment, anything”.

4.2 Negative aspects

1. **Social media:** Despite their potential, social media are frequently criticised for hate speech, polarisation, disinformation and algorithmic manipulation.

Germany: [FG.2] *“If I leave a comment on Twitter, for example, that this could have any influence? I don’t think so at all. So how am I supposed to have an influence on politics if I leave a comment? I can perhaps vent my anger there, but how am I supposed to be able to influence anything?”.*

France: [FG.3] *“PC (W, 65): I believe that the danger is that any ordinary person who does not have knowledge, who does not know their subject, who has the same access as someone informed, as a philosopher, as a doctor. And that is very, very dangerous”.*

2. **Participation through media seen as ineffective or even harmful:** Some citizens see political engagement through the media as dangerous, divisive or sterile.

Italy: [Int.25] *“Q: In your opinion, can television, newspapers and radio be a space where citizens express themselves and talk about issues affecting them, or are they closed spaces?”*

A: In my opinion, they are distant. It seems that citizens seek them more for interaction and comments, to create more of the same. Then again, I don’t use many other communication systems, except YouTube and social media, just to keep up. However, it seems to me that there is more news and comments below. News on the TV news pushes towards a type of communication and there are no comments below”.

Czech: [FG.3] *“Participant 22: Even if you get involved in the media, you still won’t achieve anything. Maybe during elections or something like that, where there’s more political power, but otherwise, the media is always influenced by someone. It will never be different”.*

Citizens recognise the potential for participation in both digital and traditional media, but express strong reservations about their actual effectiveness and the quality of the debate they generate. In particular:

- Social media is seen as a powerful participatory space but distorted by dynamics of hate, polarisation and superficiality.
- Traditional media maintain a recognised role, but one that is more passive and less interactive.

- More inclusive, regulated and transparent platforms are needed to make media participation truly meaningful.

Category	Positive Aspects	Negative Aspects
Social Media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Accessible and widely used, especially by young people - Facilitates fast mobilisation, information sharing, and online activism - Enables expression of personal opinions and community fact-checking 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Spread of hate speech, polarisation, and disinformation - Perceived lack of real political impact - Algorithmic manipulation and echo chambers
Traditional Media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Still relevant for less digitally-savvy citizens - Can attract public attention and political responses through visibility (TV, radio, newspapers) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Seen as distant, non-interactive, and controlled - Limited space for direct citizen participation
Digital Tools & Platforms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Blogs, petitions, apps, and surveys offer alternative channels for civic engagement - Support self-expression and public visibility 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Perceived as fragmented or lacking influence - Risk of superficial engagement without institutional follow-up
Overall Perception	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Media provide diverse tools for democratic participation - Can complement institutional participation when used effectively 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Quality of debate often poor- Participation feels symbolic rather than impactful

ANNEX

In this section, are listed the main categories and codes generated during the analysis. Each code is associated with a presence frequency.

Democracy idea

Freedom	144
Freedom of expression	77
Freedom of choice	22
Freedom of participation	10
Free Media	7
Liberation from fascism	3
Freedom to travel	2
Representative system	107
Majority choice	34
Political delegation	15
People power	61
Decision	25
Participation	22
Trust	1
Community	57
Mutual respect	37
Shared decisions	9
Civic responsibility	2
Inclusivity	2
Equality	32
Rights and duties	15
Abstract concept - Label	8
Process	7
Fluid Process	2
Slow process	2
Confused Process	1
Historical Process	1
Plurality of views	6

Laws	4
Protection of minorities	3
Transparency	3
Luck	2
Separation of power	2
Access to media	1
Best possible solution	1
Internationality	1
Justice	1

Democracy Opinion

Negative	609
Politics	231
Distant - selfish	78
No help for people	18
No results	4
Communication	34
Disrespectful communication	23
Ineffective communication	5
No dialogue	5
Broken promises	33
Fragmented parties	18
Disillusionment	10
Divide society	9
No ideals	9
Red herring	8
Corruption	7
Lobbies influences	15
Scandal	3
Political patronage	1
No representatives	6
Unprepared	6

No leadership	4
No equal representation	1
Citizens	113
Lack of participation	23
Lack of political identity	15
Slogan choices	6
Political disinterest	15
Pointless complaints	12
Closed mindset	11
Selfish	11
Wrong political choices	9
Lack of civic sentiment	6
Divided	5
no mutual respect	2
Controvertial discussion	4
Old mentality	1
Old votant	1
Censorship	55
From the State	22
Btw citizens	12
BTW parties	2
Inequality	40
Discrimination	13
Elitism	4
Struggle	1
Ignorance	26
No political education	12
No media education	4
Inadequate news	2
Voting system	21
Not enough referendum	4
Vote not respected	4
Not for all	2

Difficulty voting for non-residents	1
External influence	1
Propaganda choice	1
Too much referendum	2
Extremism	17
Mutual interferences	14
EU dependence	7
Church	2
Corporation influence	2
Justice system	13
Welfare system	12
Bureacracy	10
Too much freedom	10
Crime	3
Extreme opinions	3
Violence	3
Misinformation	1
Weak police	1
Immigration	8
Democracy mediatization	7
Disinformation	6
Constitution not respected	5
Low-turnout government	5
Citizens Disempowerment	4
General system that do not work	4
Generational clash	3
Utopia	2
International conflicts	1
Lack of transparency	1
Small dictatorship	1
Positive	137
Working system	25

Electoral system	23
Freedom of speech	22
Better than others	19
Better than dictatorship	5
Freedom to participate	8
Pluralism	8
Politicians	6
Better than before	4
Citizens participation	3
Inclusion	3
Accessible news	2
Constructive skepticism	2
Local politics	2
Open-mindedness	2
UE	2
Citizens help	1
Civic Awareness	1
General surveillance	1
Justice	1
New generations	1
No corruption	1

Democracy Expectation

Citizens	65
More participation	26
More Referendum	7
Ongoing consultation	7
Mandatory elections	2
Direct democracy	1
Permanent consultation	1
Younger participation	1
Media education	11

Political education	7
Civic education	6
Pluralism opinions	4
Be informed	3
Family responsibility	3
Military service	2
Dialogue with the journalist	1
Less complains	1
Political interest	1
Politics	48
Active listening	8
Local policy	7
Honesty	5
Regulation	5
Collaboration	4
Fulfill promises	4
Mutual Respect	3
Change politicians	2
Impartiality	2
Equal representation	1
More control	1
More women	1
National interest	1
political agreement	1
Political Education	1
Community interest	6
Transparency	6
Voting participation	2
Better information	5
Equality	4
Better welfare	3
Human rights concerned	3
North countries model	2

Free to protest	1
Institutional educational campaign	1
More laws	1
New democracy	1
Post capitalism	1
Revolution	1

Democracy Threats

Extremism	20
Drift in values	7
Aggressiveness	3
Lack of respect	2
Lack of cohesion	1
Superficiality	1
Critical events	4
Digital age	4
Digital divide	1
Abstentionism	3
Passive participation	2
Media	3
Social media	16
Disinformation	11
Manipulated communication	5
Echo chambers	1
Media ownership	1
Censorship	2
Popular uprising	2
Violence	2
Denial voting	1
External pressures	1
Lobbies	2
Ignorance	1

Incoherent welfare	1
Lack of listening	1
Misunderstanding	1
Polarization	1
Structural instability	1

Democracy Trust/ Distrust

Democracy distrust	145
Politics	108
Broken promises	26
Disinterest in people	17
Corruption	11
No accountability	6
No common perspectives	5
No real changes	3
Instability	2
Absenteeism	1
Denigration	1
Discrimination	1
Divisions	1
Old politicians	1
too many alliances	1
Media	10
Fake news	1
Extreme opinions	4
General distrust	4
Justice	3
No citizens power	3
Citizens disinterest	2
Hate speech	2
No future	2
Abstentionism	1

Covid	1
Discrimination	1
E-voting	1
Polarization	1
Populism	1
UE	1
Democracy trust	108
Politics	31
Benefit of the doubt	8
Proximity	3
Republic president	3
Active listening	2
Gut feeling	2
Politics preparation	2
Control	1
Free	1
New politicians	1
Similar ideals	1
Better than totalitarian	12
Democracy's ideal	11
Hope	8
Voting system	7
Freedom	6
Citizens	5
First responders	5
General system	4
Constitution	3
EU	3
Justices	3
With critical eye	3
Education	1
Generational change	1

Media	1
NGO	1
Science	1
Technical commision	1
Transparency	1

Media democratic role Idea

Impartiality	39
Properly informing	24
Watchdog	13
Political education	8
People voice	7
Promote critical thinking	5
Free	4
pluralism voices	3
Professionalism	3
Apolitical	2
Community sense	2
Independent	2
Social Cohesion	1

Opinion Media role

Negative	878
Partiality & lack of objectivity	213
Corporate control	25
Limited news	23
Social media	116
Algorithms	28
Unreliability	26
Eco chambers	16

Superficiality	12
Fake news	5
Hate speech	4
Sensationalism	4
Adv board	3
Censorship	3
Addiction	2
Privacy data	2
Too negative	2
Bias	1
Not accessible	1
Useless discussions	1
Low quality	83
Superficial news	33
Disrespectful discussions	19
Controversial guests	5
Boring programmes	4
Unprepared journalists	4
Generalizations	3
No quality control	3
Confusion	2
Lack of political tribunes	2
No dialogue	2
Subdued election info	1
Lack of reliability	81
Disinformation	29
Manipulation	24
Contradictory news	7
Opinion makers	5
Pre-established discussions	5
Data privacy	2
Lack of credible sources	2
Corporate scandal	1

Extreme narractions	1
Earning logic	72
Clickbait	21
Precarius work	2
Advertisement	1
TV	66
Partiality	27
no dialogue	8
Poor formats	8
Superficiality	6
Old format	5
Sensationalism	5
difficult debates	3
Not enough politics	1
Populism	1
Too negative news	47
Public media	31
Public funding	1
Censorship	26
Not enough political info	18
Minimized political participation coverage	12
Not enough local info	2
Too much news	15
Emotional impact	14
Echo chambers	13
No transparency	13
External control	12
No help for citizens	12
Ignoring people's reality	8
Subscription	11
Difficoult information	10
Discrimination	6
No minorities attention	3

Media education	3
over political coverage	3
Digital poverty	2
Media barriers	2
Too local perspective	2
Too much freedom	2
No citizen participation	1
Not enough expert	1
Print	1
Too many newspapers	1
UE negative	1
Positive	91
Social media	17
Fast	6
Easy political info	5
Impartiality	3
Young target	3
Freedom of expression	2
Pluralism	2
Encourage discussion	1
Public media	13
Neutrality	9
Balanced partiality	6
Citizens participation	8
Citizens support	5
Clear information	5
Free	5
TV	5
Political debates	3
Fact checking	2
Slow news	3
Electoral surveys	2

Institutional control	2
Local news	2
Podcast	2
Political investigation	2
Print	2
Public awareness campaigns	2
Radio	2
Critical trust	1
Democracy representation	1
News on protest	1
Online news	1

Media Expectations

Impartiality & objectivity	52
Quality	38
Less negative news	13
Higher quality programmes	11
Less commercial	7
Gender sensitive approach	3
Better news order	1
Details - Data	1
Less humor	1
Transparency	23
Social media	21
Regulation	7
Young target	6
Free comments	2
More political info	2
Responsability	2
No political info	1
Regulation	19
Referendum	1

Diversification	14
In depth journalism	14
More citizen participation	13
More political participation news	3
Educational programmes	10
Indipendency	10
Economic indipendency	1
Attention on ordinary people	8
Plurality	8
Fact checking	7
Institutional channel	5
Watchdogs	5
Constructive discussions	4
More solution	4
Public media	4
Apolitical public media	2
Free public media	2
Honesty	3
Journalism training	3
Local news	2
More political news	2
More political debates	4
Uncomfortable questions for politicians	2
More welfare indication	2
Scientific sources	2
Accessibility	1
Accessible political news	23
Journalism identity	1
No polls	1
Specialization	1

Media Social Impact

Social media	18
Echo chambers	7
Young generation	5
Resentment	1
Democracy influence	12
Citizen opinion	51
Citizens Participation	25
Citizens engagement	15
Manipulation	8
Politics	5
TV - Old generation	5
Political bubbles	4
Political education	4
emotional impact	3
Demotivation	2
Extreme opinions	2
Prejudices	2
No impact	1
Social struggles	1

Media Trust/Distrust

Media trust	202
Traditional media	34
TV	13
Radio	11
Print	8
Local papers	1
Social media	29
Yuotube	6
communitty check	2
Professional media profiles	2

Institutional social media profiles	1
Public media	27
Journalist	22
Professionalism	17
Personality	4
Indipendency	18
Website	14
Impartiality	12
Critical consumption	9
Authority	6
Foreign media	6
Institutional sources	4
News agency	4
Scientific sources	4
General trust	3
Private media	3
Headlines	2
Selective exposure	2
Tabloid	2
Inclusivity	1
Media distrust	61
General skepticism	29
Social media	11
Partiality	10
Eco chamber effects	4
AI	3
Sensationalism	3
Clickbait	1
Controlled	1
Mistakes	1
Traditional media	1
TV	7

Private channel	3
Too negative news	1
Unprecised	1

Media Habits

Diversification	94
Multiple outlets	70
Different perspectives	22
Critical eye	34
Indipendent research	30
Always check	22
Passive consumption	12
Avoid news	5
Subscription	5
Faster option	2
Media bubbles	2

Political Participation – Activities

Protests & Strikes	79
Voting	77
Referendum	12
Informing yourself	33
Discussing with others	26
Involvements in politics	19
Civic associations	16
Volunteering	20
Community life	18
Citizens' committees	11
Petitions	16
Citizen consultations	12
Conference on the Future of Europe	3
Contacting politicians	11

Education	7
Social responsibility	7
Solidarity	5
Spreading knowledge	5
Cultural discussion	4
Following the rules	4
Non voting	4
Personal choice	4
Critical perspectives	3
Financial support for independent entities	3
Work	3
Contacting the media	2
Debunking populists	2
Getting heard	2
Activism	1
Boycotting	2
Avoid the media	2
Trade unionism	1

Political Participation – Obstacles

Skepticism	169
Politics	103
Broken promises	35
Citizens not listened to	17
Lack of representation	17
Corruption	7
Distance	5
Europe far away	6
Unprepared representatives	5
Mutual polemics	4
Disrespectful	3
Citizen power	65

Media	43
Insufficient political info	32
No news on citizens activities	6
No young target	5
Too biased information	2
Negative news	4
Low quality	2
Exageration	1
Partiality	1
Slogan information	1
Fear	39
Hate speech	10
Legal ripercussion	7
State violence	6
Critics	5
Shame	5
Personal safety	2
Prejudices	2
To do the wrong choice	1
Political disinterest	33
Selfishness	22
Social distance	1
Difficulties in voting	20
Time constraints	6
Voting away from home	6
Difficult communication	5
Backlogged voting system	1
Economic gap	1
Ignorance	11
General frustration	9
No political education	9
No time	9
Controvercial topic	6

Distrust of unions	5
Economic situation	5
Loss of Values	5
Censorship	4
Politically correct	2
Confusion	4
General well-being	4
Disrespect election choice	3
Political compromises	3
Digital divide	2
Elitism	2
Family education	2
Inequalities	2
Privacy	2
Burocracy	1
Depopulation	1
No strike tradition	1
Non organization	1
Polls	1

Political Participation – Encouragements

Politics	54
Active listening	20
Political Transparency	6
promises kept	5
Know the politicians	4
More local debates	4
New politicians	3
Accessibility	2
Less fragmentation	2
Realistic goals	2
Clearer communication	1

Collaborative debates	1
Minority representatives	1
Political personalities	1
Professionalism	1
Support citizens participation	1
Media	47
Simple and better	14
Social media	9
News on citizens activities	5
Fair debates	3
News transparency	3
Accessibility	2
ADV democracy	2
Positive news	2
younger target	2
Balanced news	1
Institutional campaigns	1
Iterative communication	1
Pluralism	1
Voting	21
Facilitate voting	7
Direct democracy	4
Referendum	4
Mandatory elections	2
Better choices	1
Different electoral system	1
Electronic voting	1
Maximum age	1
Proximity	13
French participation model	10
Results	10
More cohesion	8
Costructive discussion	7

Incentives	4
Motivators	3
Volunteering adv	3
Justice	2
More citizen power	2
Mutual respect	2
Solidarity	2
Anonymity	1
Living in the city	1
More time	1
More visibility	1
Non-partisan activities	1
Populism	1
Positive gathering	1
Written protest	1
Education	0
Political education	30
Younger education	3
Debate education	2
Family education	1

Participation through the media

Social media	121
Negative	42
Social media	31
Hate speech	12
Limited power	10
Polarization	5
Algorithm disincentive	3
Dangerous	1
Useless power	9
Avoid the media	1

No dialogue	1
Traditional	35
TV	21
Radio	9
Online platforms	8
Letters to newspapers	6
Surveys	5
Community fact checking	4
Online petitions	4
Online newspapers	3
Blog	2
Economic donation	2
Online Comments	2
Podcast	2
App	1
Local newspaper	1